

Atlantic Ecosystems Assessment, Forecasting & Sustainability

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Table of Content

1	Version History	5
2	Executive summary	6
3	Introduction	7
4	Dissemination & Adoption of the Best Practices	8
5	Guiding principles	10
5.1	International System of Units	10
5.2	Tara Oceans end-to-end protocols	11
6	System of Biological Entities that compose the Ocean Microbiome	14
7	Ocean Microbiome – Standard Operating Procedures (OM-SOPs)	16
	Summary Table I - Ocean Microbiome - Standard Operating Procedures (OM-SOPs)	17
8	Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO Protocols	20
	Summary Table II - AtlantECO protocols	21
	Chemistry – SAL – Salinity	25
	Chemistry – NUT-1 – Nutrients V1 – Oceano. Rosette	26
	Chemistry – NUT-2 – Nutrients V2	27
	Chemistry – NUT-3 – Nutrients V3 – Underway	28
	Chemistry – DINO – d15Nitrate & d18Oxygen V1	29
	Chemistry – DGAS – Dissolved Gasses	30
	Chemistry – DO18 – d18Oxygen Isotopes	31
	Chemistry – DIC13 – DIC & d13Carbon Isotopes	32
	Chemistry – DICTA – DIC & Total Alkalinity	33
	Chemistry – MTE-F – Marine Trace Elements – Filtered	34
	Chemistry – MTE-T – Marine Trace Elements – Total	35
	Chemistry – HG-T – Total Mercury (Hg)	36
	Chemistry – HG-M – Methylmercury (MeHg)	37
	Chemistry – HG – Particulate Mercury (Hg)	38
	Chemistry – NPO45 – targeting nanoplastic	39
	Chemistry – NP550 – targeting very small microplastic	39
	Chemistry – CP50 – chemistry of microplastics	39
	Chemistry – CP200 – chemistry of microplastics	41
	Chemistry – CP330 – chemistry of microplastics	42
	BioGeoChemistry – PM – Particulate Matter (PN/POC/d13C/d15N)	43
	BioGeoChemistry – PM20 – Particulate Matter (PN/POC/d13C/d15N)	44
	BioGeoChemistry – PM200 – Particulate Matter (PN/POC/d13C/d15N)	45
	Genomics – HC – virus Hi-C sequencing	46
	Genomics – S<02 – targeting viruses	47
	Genomics – eDNA – targeting large Eukaryotes	48
	Genetics – SG – single-organism-genomics pico/nano	49

Genomics – Aerosols AS – metabarcoding	50
Genomics – Aerosols AF – size-fractionated metabarcoding	51
Genomics – S025-L – targeting prokaryotes	52
Genomics – S023 – targeting prokaryotes	53
Genomics – S320 – targeting unicellular eukaryotes	53
Genomics – S520-L – targeting unicellular eukaryotes	54
Genomics – S20 – Genomics micro	55
Genomics – S20-L – targeting unicellular eukaryotes	56
Genomics – S200 – Genomics	57
Genomics – S200-L – targeting unicellular eukaryotes	58
Genomics – SP300 – sequencing the plastisphere	59
Genomics – S680-L (B) – targeting unicellular eukaryotes	60
Genomics – S680-L (A) – Genomics	61
Proteomics – PT023 – targeting prokaryotes	62
Proteomics – PT320 – targeting unicellular eukaryotes	62
Metabolomics – MB<02 – targeting exometabolites	63
Metabolomics – MB023 – targeting prokaryotes	63
Metabolomics – MB320 – targeting unicellular eukaryotes	63
Metabolomics – MB20 – targeting unicellular eukaryotes	66
Phenomics – HP – pigments (HPLC)	67
Phenomics – FC – flow-cytometry pico/nano	68
Phenomics – Aerosols AI – Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)	69
Phenomics – FM5 – e-HCFM nano	70
Phenomics – SEM – Scanning Electron Microscopy – pico/nano	71
Phenomics & Genomics – E5 – single-organism-genomics micro	72
Phenomics – 3DEM5 – 3D electron microscopy nano	73
Phenomics – FCAM20 – FlowCam 4x	74
Phenomics & Genomics – E20 – single-organism-genomics micro	75
Phenomics – FM20 – e-HCFM micro	76
Phenomics – 3DEM20 – 3D electron microscopy micro	77
Phenomics – LU20 – taxonomy	78
Phenomics – F200 – ZooScan	79
Phenomics & Genomics – E200 – sorting single-organism	80
Phenomics – MP300 – Microscopic imaging of the plastisphere	81
Phenomics – F680 & F2000 – ZooScan	82
Phenomics & Genomics – E2000 – sorting single organisms	83
Phenomics & Genomics – E680 & E2000 – sorting single organisms	84
12 Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO – Sampling flowcharts	86

1 Version History

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
1	S. Pesant (EMBL-EBI)	D4.1 Handbook V1	24.05.2021
1.2	S. Pesant (EMBL-EBI)	Addition of sample collection protocols package	01.05.2022
1.3	E. Muxagata (FURG) & D. Johns (MBA)	Addition of CPR collection protocols package	01.05.2022
1.4	J. Poulain (CEA)	Addition of genetic analysis protocols package	01.06.2022
1.5	A. Elineau (SU)	Addition of imaging analysis protocols package	01.06.2022
1.6	M. Huete (EMBRC-UVIGO) J. Schramm (FTO)	Addition of ABS protocols package	01.07.2022
1.7	S. Pesant (EMBL-EBI)	Text updated with AtlantECO protocols	30.07.2024
2.0	S. Pesant (EMBL-EBI)	D4.4 Handbook finalised	16.02.2026

2 Executive summary

The present deliverable (D4.4) reports on AtlantECO's Handbook of Standards and Best Practices. It was developed throughout the project, and its content is presented in three deliverables (D4.1, D4.2 & D4.4), which are all publicly accessible under a single DOI (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4897860>) and also available via UNESCO's Ocean Best Practices. AtlantECO generated new observations as part of the project's sampling activities in synergy with other European and International projects (see deliverable D4.7). The Handbook provides a set of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for methodologies used across these activities to study the Ocean microbiome. These SOPs also constitute a basis for comparing protocols and aggregating results from different observation programmes. The SOPs are generic and describe key methodological concepts, materials and procedural steps, which gives the different observation programmes enough flexibility to adopt the standards and best practices and adapt the SOPs to their specific context.

The Handbook includes in deliverable D4.1 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4897861>):

- Guiding principles for the design of AtlantECO's Standards & Best Practices
- A filtration kit for key genomics, proteomics and metabolomics protocols
- An imaging kit for key phenomics protocols

The Handbook includes in deliverable D4.2 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6956974>) a collection of five downloadable packages:

- Sampling protocols from Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO
- Sampling protocols from AtlantECO's Brazil-South-Africa line of the Continuous Plankton Recorder
- Analysis protocols for metabarcoding, metagenomics and metatranscriptomics
- Analysis protocols for imaging
- Access and Benefits Sharing protocols

The Handbook includes in deliverable D4.4 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18801151>):

- Revised guiding principles for the design of AtlantECO's Standards & Best Practices
- A revised System of Biological Entities composing the Ocean Microbiome
- Ocean Microbiome - Standard Operating Procedures published on protocols.io
- 62 one-page protocols from Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO, also published on protocols.io

The most significant impact and legacy of AtlantECO's Handbook of Standards and Best Practices is the publication of the Ocean Microbiome - Standard Operating Procedures (OM-SOPs) at protocols.io, an online platform widely used in research to cite, share, discover and use reproducible methods. Each OM-SOP is published as a collection that can branch into many equivalent or derived protocols. These branches can be established with already existing protocols, such as those from project Tara Oceans, or can be created new as we did for Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO. As a legacy, EMBL-EBI will continue to curate the OM-SOPs at protocols.io, and to invite and help other projects to branch in their own protocols into the OM-SOPs, including EMBC's [EMO-BON](https://protocols.io), EMBL's TRaversing the European Coastline ([TREC](https://protocols.io)) and [EC|BIOcean5D](https://protocols.io).

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction

The AtlantECO Project aims to study the Atlantic Ocean from pole to pole to determine the structure and function of the Atlantic microbiome in the context of ocean circulation and presence of pollutants to assess 1) its role in driving the dynamics of Atlantic ecosystems at basin and regional scales; 2) its potential to act as an indicator of ecosystem status and 3) the mechanism by which it drives the provision of ecosystem services.

In order to deliver this, the Project builds on four activity streams (AS):

- **AS1 - Assess the status of the ecosystem structures, functions, health and services** at regional, basin and all Atlantic scales and provide high quality gridded data products and maps;
- **AS2 - Enhance knowledge and innovate** by adopting standard optical and genetic observations protocols, cutting-edge network analysis methods and better parametrisation of connectivity and biogeochemical models;
- **AS3 - Assess drivers and stressors of change and forecast** their impact on tipping points and recovery of ecosystem structures, functions and services and develop eco-socio-economic models to predict their future states;
- **AS4 - Share and use** capacity and knowledge across the four continents bordering the Atlantic Ocean ensuring a seamless engagement between science, industry, policy and society.

AtlantECO is organised around three pillars of research: **marine microbiomes, plastics and the plastisphere** and **seascape and connectivity**, and focuses on five ecosystem services:

- **ES1:** Climate support system: carbon drawdown and storage
- **ES2:** Deep ocean life support system: transfer of matter & energy to mesopelagic and seabed ecosystems.
- **ES3:** Food security and the trophic fluxes: fisheries and aquaculture.
- **ES4:** Healthy planet, healthy people: biohazards, cycling of plastics and pollutants
- **ES5:** Biodiversity: resilience, adaptation and contribution to the Bioeconomy, including new chemicals

The Project addressed how the three pillars of research, together affect the ecology, biodiversity, sensitivity to climate change and the sustainability of the five ecosystem services.

As part of its second activity stream (AS2), AtlantECO generated new observations about its three pillars of research. These observations were obtained from a wide range of sampling platforms, including public and private research vessels (AtlantECO's flagship cruises), coastal and offshore observatories (AtlantECO's All Atlantic Ocean Sampling day), and citizen sail boats (AtlantECO's citizen Sail for Science). In addition, a number of synergies with other European and International projects contributed additional observations.

AtlantECO aimed at harmonising as much as possible the methodologies used across these activities by developing standards and best practices organised in a Handbook and disseminated to other European and international projects, and more widely via UNESCO's Ocean Best Practices System and the online platform Protocols.io.

4 Dissemination & Adoption of the Best Practices

The value of a best practice can be measured by the degree to which it is adopted by its users. Already, the sampling protocols published in AtlantECO's Handbook of Standards and Best Practices (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4897860>) have inspired, and in many cases were replicated by a number of European and international initiatives such as EMBRC's [EMO-BON](#), EMBL's Traversing the European Coastline ([TREC](#)), [EuroSea](#) and [EC|BIOcean5D](#). In addition, AtlantECO's Handbook of Standards and Best Practices are now part of UNESCO's Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS)¹.

Figure 1. The framework proposed by OPBS for the adoption of best practices²

The most significant dissemination vector for the adoption AtlantECO's Standards and Best Practices is the publication of the Ocean Microbiome - Standard Operating Procedures (OM-SOPs) at protocols.io, an online platform widely used in research to cite, share, discover and use reproducible methods. Each OM-SOP is published as a collection that can branch into many equivalent or derived protocols. These branches can be established with already existing protocols, such as those from project Tara Oceans, or can be created new as we did for Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO. As a legacy, EMBL-EBI will continue to curate the OM-SOPs at protocols.io, and to invite and help other projects to branch in their own protocols into the OM-SOPs, including EMBRC's [EMO-BON](#), EMBL's Traversing the European Coastline ([TREC](#)), [BioGeoScapes](#) and [EC|BIOcean5D](#).

In addition to publishing AtlantECO's OM-SOPs on protocols.io (see Section 7) and publishing sampling protocols from Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO (see Section 8) on protocols.io, the packages of genomic and imaging analysis protocols included in D4.2 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6956974>) were published on protocols.io:

- Genomics – Handling-of-genomics-samples ([link to protocols.io](#))
- Genomics – Nucleic-acids-preparations ([link to protocols.io](#))
- Genomics – Sequencing-library-preparation ([link to protocols.io](#))
- Genomics – Sequencing-and-data-quality-control ([link to protocols.io](#))

¹ <https://www.oceanbestpractices.org/>

² Hörstmann et al. (2020) Towards a Best Practice for Developing Best Practices in Ocean Observation (BP4BP). IOC Manuals and Guides No.84 (IOC/2020/MG/84). <http://dx.doi.org/10.25607/OBP-781>

- Genomics – 18s-and-16s-rna-genes-amplicon-generation-for-eukaryotes ([link to protocols.io](https://www.protocols.io))
- Genomics – Dna-and-rna-backups ([link to protocols.io](https://www.protocols.io))
- Genomics – Viral-to-metazoan-marine-plankton-nucleotide-sequencing ([link to protocols.io](https://www.protocols.io))
- Phenomics – Simple-3d-imaging-of-biogenic-silica-structures ([link to protocols.io](https://www.protocols.io))
- Phenomics – Planktoscope-protocol-for-plankton-imaging ([link to protocols.io](https://www.protocols.io))

5 Guiding principles

Funding bodies, the industry and the scientific community largely endorse the principle that best practices and common standards underpin reproducibility, ensuring that the relevant elements of a methodology are used consistently and generate results of the highest quality. Even though standards and best practices should stand on their own, they should also function well together and facilitate the integration of pre-existing protocols.

Best practices are generally defined in a bottom-up fashion, by a community, for a community, and commonly take the form of community handbooks, cookbooks, guidelines, manuals and standard operating procedures (SOPs). While the emergence of best practices is essential to support innovation, the many best practices adopted across different communities are often fragmented, with gaps and duplication, which often limits their combined use. **The first objective of AtlantECO's Handbook was to include its community best practices and protocols that are relevant to its three pillars of research in order to support its various sampling activities.**

Standards on the other hand are generally defined in a top-down fashion by authoritative bodies such as the International Standards Organisation (ISO), and they may serve as important benchmarks to evaluate best practices. The ISO defines standards as “documents of requirements, specifications, guidelines or characteristics that can be used consistently to ensure that materials, products, processes and services are fit for their purpose.” **The second objective of AtlantECO's Handbook was to analyse the various community standards and propose a coherent system of Ocean Microbiome Standard Operating Procedures.**

AtlantECO used a pragmatic approach to rapidly deploy a first suite of community specific best practices & protocols across its activities in order to reach its goals, while working on the developing standards to aggregate and harmonise best practices and protocols from other communities. AtlantECO's system of Ocean Microbiome Standard Operating Procedures (OM-SOP) was inspired by the *International System of Units*³, and is based on the pioneering work of the *Tara Oceans expedition*⁴ and the *European project MicroB3*⁵.

5.1 International System of Units

The International System of Units (SI, abbreviated from the French *Système international d'unités*) is the modern form of the metric system. It is the only system of measurement with an official status in nearly every country in the world. It comprises a coherent system of units of measurement starting with seven base units. The system allows for an unlimited number of additional units, called derived units, which can always be represented as combinations of the base units. Nine derived units are given as an example in Figure 2.

The SI also provides twenty prefixes to the unit names and unit symbols that facilitate the nomenclature and semantic of the system. The SI is intended to be an evolving system; units and prefixes are created and unit definitions are modified through international agreement as the technology of measurement progresses and the precision of measurements improves.

³ International Bureau of Weights and Measures (2006), *The International System of Units (SI)*, ISBN 92-822-2213-6

⁴ Karsenti et al. (2011) A Holistic Approach to Marine Eco-Systems Biology. *PLoS Biol* 9(10): e1001177. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1001177>

⁵ Ten Hoopen et al. (2015) Marine microbial biodiversity, bioinformatics and biotechnology (M2B3) data reporting and service standards. *Stand Genomic Sci.* 10(20). <https://dx.doi.org/10.1186%2Fs40793-015-0001-5>

International System of Units (SI)

Figure 2. The seven base units and examples of derived units from the International System of units.

5.2 Tara Oceans end-to-end protocols⁶

The aim of Tara Oceans was to sample most of the global ocean's biogeographic provinces and to follow standardised protocols in order to facilitate comparative analysis. Seawater was sampled from the sunlit, epipelagic zone and from the dark, mesopelagic zone using water bottles, pumps and nets down to 1,000 m. Plankton were separated according to their size using sieves and filtering membranes, and were preserved in liquid nitrogen or with different fixatives for molecular and/or morphological analyses. Back in the laboratory, nucleic acids were extracted from the filters and subjected to high-throughput sequencing (HTS) to generate metabarcoding (metaB), metagenomic (metaG) and metatranscriptomic (metaT) data sets as well as to yield single-cell genomes. Deep sequencing was performed with Illumina technology at high coverage rates per sample to assess the genomic content of plankton species, including those that are rare in the environment. Other samples were analysed with high-throughput imaging (HTI) methods to determine the taxonomy of plankton across size fractions spanning seven orders of magnitude, and to quantify their abundance, cellular biovolumes and other morphological attributes.

High-throughput sequencing (HTS) and imaging (HTS) are complementary, but they are rarely sampled concurrently and combined for analysis. Together, they offer powerful means to reveal how environmental and/or genomic variability impacts organismal or cellular phenotypes, and to generate hypotheses about the nature of physical interactions between organisms.

⁶ Sunagawa et al. (2020) Tara Oceans: towards global ocean ecosystems biology. *Nat Rev Microbiol* 18, 428–445. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41579-020-0364-5>

Figure 3. The base entities (middle part), and a range of sequencing analysis methods (top) and imaging analysis methods (bottom) targeted by the sampling strategies of Tara Oceans (reproduced from Suanagawa et al. 2020).

High Throughput Sequencing (HTS) included metabarcoding (metaB) sequencing to provide a baseline survey of the diversity and relative abundance of prokaryotic and eukaryotic taxa in their environmental context. In addition, metagenomic (metaG) and metatranscriptomic (metaT) sequencing were performed to uncover the genomic potential and expression of genes in viruses, prokaryotes, and eukaryotes, with the additional advantage of gaining insights into the population structure and evolution of, and selective pressure on, the most abundant planktonic organisms in the ocean. Finally, additional efforts went into the sequencing of new draft genomes from single cells of protists and bacteria that were isolated by flow cytometry from cryopreserved seawater samples, as well as of individual zooplankton organisms.

High-Throughput Imaging (HTI) was achieved using a series of automated imaging methods to quantify the concentration, biomass, biovolume, taxonomic composition, and morphological features of plankton, as well as suspended and sinking particles across organismal size fractions. These methods included the Underwater Vision Profiler, ZooScan, FlowCAM, Imaging FlowCytobot, and e-HCFM, an environmental high-content fluorescence microscopy workflow developed during the project. Together, these technologies allowed for

automated imaging of organisms across different taxonomic and functional groups ranging in size from individual cells to large gelatinous zooplankton and marine snow particles.

AtlantECO's ambition was to go beyond the transformative contribution of Tara Oceans by augmenting current ocean observation best practices with a set of protocols for the study of marine proteomics and metabolomics, using high throughput mass spectrometry.

High Throughput Mass Spectrometry (HTMS) plays a central role in advancing marine proteomics and metabolomics by enabling the rapid, sensitive, and comprehensive analysis of complex biological samples from ocean environments. Marine organisms often live in dynamic and extreme conditions, requiring sophisticated molecular adaptations that can only be understood through large-scale protein and metabolite profiling. High-resolution mass spectrometry allows researchers to identify thousands of proteins and metabolites simultaneously, even at very low concentrations in seawater, sediments, or biological tissues. In marine proteomics, it reveals protein expression patterns, post-translational modifications, and stress-response mechanisms. In metabolomics, it uncovers biochemical pathways involved in nutrient cycling, symbiosis, toxin production, and environmental adaptation. Automated workflows and advanced bioinformatics tools further enhance data processing and interpretation. By supporting ecosystem monitoring, climate change research, and marine biotechnology discovery, high-throughput spectrometry provides critical molecular insights into ocean health and biodiversity.

Figure 4. The multi-omics approach of AtlantECO includes the study of genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics and phenomics or the expression of biological traits (not shown on the figure), using high throughput sequencing, spectrometry and imaging techniques.

6 System of Biological Entities that compose the Ocean Microbiome

AtlantECO proposes a System of Entities that partitions the Ocean Microbiome into a continuum of seven categories of biological entities. Each category targets a group of biological entities according to their organisation at molecular, cellular and community scales, and according to their size.

Figure 5. Schematics of AtlantECO's System of Entities that partitions the Ocean Microbiome into a continuum of seven categories of biological entities. Each category targets a group of biological entities according to their organisation at molecular, cellular and community scales, and according to their size.

The seven partitions target:

1. **molecules** in the size range 0.002-0.02, which are of biological origin, and comprise free DNA, RNA, proteins and metabolites
2. **viruses** in the size range 0.02-0.2 μm , which lack a nucleus and bear only RNA or DNA, but not both
3. **prokaryotes** in the size range 0.2-2 μm , which lack a nucleus but bear both DNA and RNA
4. **eukaryotes** in the size range 2-20 μm , which have a nucleus and bear both DNA and RNA, and essentially comprise unicellular organisms
5. **eukaryotes** in the size range 20-200 μm , which have a nucleus and bear both DNA and RNA, and comprise unicellular, colonial and some multicellular organisms
6. **eukaryotes** in the size range 200-2000 μm , which have a nucleus and bear both DNA and RNA, and comprise essentially multicellular and occasionally large or colonial unicellular organisms
7. **eukaryotes** in the size range >2000 μm , which have a nucleus and bear both DNA and RNA, and comprise the occasional large organisms caught in plankton nets, e.g. salps, jellyfish and fish larvae

The complexity of biological entities cannot simply be resolved by finite size partitions, and as a result, entities and processes can span several of the proposed partitions. This is depicted by four outer rings on Figure 5, illustrating that biological entities from the four smaller size fractions are often present in other partitions as a result of biological associations such as symbiosis, parasitism, aggregation, or sometimes as a result of methodological biases. Molecular entities include sequencing protocols such as eDNA, which aims to be all encompassing and may even target organisms outside the realm of the Ocean microbiome such as fish, reptiles, birds and mammals.

General principles behind the partitioning of biological entities:

- *Biological entities are partitioned according to their organisation at molecular, cellular and community scales.*
- *Biological entities are partitioned according to their size, encompassing the end-to-end, continuous size spectrum of the Ocean Microbiome*
- *The complexity of biological entities cannot be simply resolved by finite partitions, and as a result, entities and processes can span several of the proposed partitions.*

7 Ocean Microbiome – Standard Operating Procedures (OM-SOPs)

Standard Operational Procedures (SOPs) for the study of the Ocean Microbiome (OM) are proposed based on the System of Biological Entities and the multi-omics approach described above.

The label of AtlantECO's OM-SOPs is composed of one letter designating the target analysis, i.e. the letter “E” for environment, “G” for genomics, “P” for proteomics, “M” for metabolomics, and “T” for trait expression or phenomics, followed by one to several digits designating the lower threshold of the size fraction (Summary Table I). Even though, in practice, the sampling gear and the membranes used to partition biological entities may vary in mesh or pore size, the standard label of the OM-SOP is generic. For example, membranes with pores size 1 or 3 μm and nets with mesh size 5 μm are often used interchangeably to separate the second and third partitions of biological entities in genomic protocols, but the OM-SOP label of all these derived protocols is consistently “G2” and its target size fraction is consistently “2-20 μm ”. This practice, once implemented in metadata records, will considerably improve the comparison of various protocols and the integration of results from similar protocols used by different observation programmes.

Summary Table I lists the OM-SOPs, specifying their targets in terms of biological entities, size fractionation, the required volume of seawater, processing time, and preservation methods. The Handbook (see D4.2) recommends specific equipment, consumables and best practices to reach the various targets. However, standards may take years to be adopted by the community, and we recognise that for a number of good reasons such as lack of capacity or consistency with historical practices, community best practices may differ from those targets. Such cases will constitute “derived protocols”. The system of OM-SOPs or “base protocols” aims to provide benchmarks against which various methodologies and best practices can be assessed, and as much as possible to provide an intercomparison between derived and base protocols. In all cases, the specificity of derived protocols is documented in the provenance metadata of the samples, according to MiXS and M2B3 reporting standards.

Summary Table I - Ocean Microbiome - Standard Operating Procedures (OM-SOPs)

multi-omics discipline	OM-SOP acronym	OM-SOP size-fraction	OM-SOP target entity	Ocean Microbiome - Standard Operating Procedure Title	OM-SOP publication (citation: doi)	target volume (L)	target Time (min)	target preservation
Genomics	G002	0.02-0.2	viruses	Ocean Microbiome SOP – G002 – Genomics protocols targeting viruses in the 0.02-0.2 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io/kqdg3nwn7v25/v1 (preview)	20	Flocculated 4-24h	+4°C
Genomics	G02	0.2-2	prokaryotes	Ocean Microbiome SOP – G02 – Genomics protocols targeting prokaryotes in the 0.2-2 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io/x54v9bobzl3e/v1 (preview)	20	< 15	LN ₂ or -80°C
Genomics	G2	2-20	eukaryotes	Ocean Microbiome SOP – G2 – Genomics protocols targeting unicellular eukaryotes in the 2-20 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io/.14egn1y1qv5d/v1 (preview)	20	< 15	LN ₂ or -80°C
Genomics	G20	20-200	eukaryotes	Ocean Microbiome SOP – G20 – Genomics protocols targeting eukaryotes in the 20-200 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io/.5jyl8xqx7v2w/v1 (preview)	10 ² -10 ⁴	< 15	LN ₂ or -80°C
Genomics	G200	200-2,000	eukaryotes	Ocean Microbiome SOP – G200 – Genomics protocols targeting eukaryotes in the 200-2,000 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io/.8epv55o54v1b/v1 (preview)	10 ³ -10 ⁵	< 15	LN ₂ or -80°C
Genomics	G2000	2,000-20,000	eukaryotes	Ocean Microbiome SOP – G2000 – Genomics protocols targeting eukaryotes in the >2,000-20,000 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io/.261ge181yv47/v1 (preview)	10 ³ -10 ⁵	< 15	LN ₂ or -80°C
Proteomics	P02	0.2-2	prokaryotes	Ocean Microbiome SOP – P02 – Proteomics protocols targeting prokaryotes in the 0.2-2 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io/.kxygx8qxkv8j/v1 (preview)	20	< 15	LN ₂ or -80°C
Proteomics	P2	2-20	eukaryotes	Ocean Microbiome SOP – P2 – Proteomics protocols targeting unicellular eukaryotes in the 2-20 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io/.q26g7797qgwz/v1 (preview)	20	< 15	LN ₂ or -80°C

multi-omics discipline	OM-SOP acronym	OM-SOP size-fraction	OM-SOP target entity	Ocean Microbiome - Standard Operating Procedure Title	OM-SOP publication (citation: doi)	target volume (L)	target Time (min)	target preservation
Metabolomics	M0002	0.002-0.02	(exo) metabolites in seawater	Ocean Microbiome SOP – M0002 – Metabolomics protocols targeting environmental exometabolites in the 0.002-0.02 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.yxmvm1mjnv3p/v1 (preview)	4x2	<60	-20°C
Metabolomics	M02	0.2-2	(endo) metabolites in prokaryotes	Ocean Microbiome SOP – M02 – Metabolomics protocols targeting prokaryotes in the 0.2-2 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.n92ld1ne9l5b/v1 (preview)	20	<15	-20°C
Metabolomics	M2	2-20	(endo) metabolites in eukaryotes	Ocean Microbiome SOP – M2 – Metabolomics protocols targeting unicellular eukaryotes in the 2-20 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.6qpvyqzognk/v1 (preview)	20	<15	-20°C
Metabolomics	M20	20-200	(endo) metabolites in eukaryotes	Ocean Microbiome SOP – M20 – Metabolomics protocols targeting eukaryotes in the 20-200 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.dm6gp1q6jgzp/v1 (preview)	10 ² -10 ⁴	<15	-20°C
Metabolomics	M200	200-2,000	(endo) metabolites in eukaryotes	Ocean Microbiome SOP – M200 – Metabolomics protocols targeting eukaryotes in the 2-20 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.e6nvwng7dvmk/v1 (preview)	10 ³ -10 ⁵	<15	-20°C
Phenomics / Traits	T002	0.02-0.2	viruses	Ocean Microbiome SOP – T002 – Phenomics/Traits protocols targeting viruses in the 0.02-0.2 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.n2bvj1bmnvk5/v1 (preview)	10 ³	na	LN2 or -80°C
Phenomics / Traits	T02	0.2-2	prokaryotes	Ocean Microbiome SOP – T02 – Phenomics/Traits protocols targeting prokaryotes in the 0.2-2 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.3byl481yzvo5/v1 (preview)	10 ³	na	LN2 or -80°C
Phenomics / Traits	T2	2-20	eukaryotes	Ocean Microbiome SOP – T2 – Phenomics/Traits protocols targeting unicellular eukaryotes in the 2-20 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.5qpvo1w49g4o/v1 (preview)	10 ²	na	+4°C

multi-omics discipline	OM-SOP acronym	OM-SOP size-fraction	OM-SOP target entity	Ocean Microbiome - Standard Operating Procedure Title	OM-SOP publication (citation: doi)	target volume (L)	target Time (min)	target preservation
Phenomics / Traits	T20	20-200	eukaryotes	Ocean Microbiome SOP – T20 – Phenomics/Traits protocols targeting eukaryotes in the 20-200 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.36wgq1qkovk5/v1 (preview)	10 ² -10 ⁴	na	live
Phenomics / Traits	T200	200-2,000	eukaryotes	Ocean Microbiome SOP – T200 – Phenomics/Traits protocols targeting eukaryotes in the 200-2,000 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. 2026 dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.4r3l2zpr3l1y/v1 (preview)	10 ³ -10 ⁵	na	formal-dehyde
Phenomics / Traits	T2000	2,000-20,000	eukaryotes	Ocean Microbiome SOP – T2000 – Phenomics/Traits protocols targeting eukaryotes in the 2,000-20,000 µm size-fraction	Pesant et al. (2026) dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.kqdg3nwo1v25/v1 (preview)	10 ³ -10 ⁵	na	ethanol

8 Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO Protocols

The first objective of AtlantECO's Handbook was to include its community best practices and protocols that are relevant to its three pillars of research in order to support its various sampling activities.

AtlantECO's flagship expedition Mission Microbiomes was the template for the implementation of an end-to-end set of protocols that target the full size and taxonomic spectrum of the Ocean microbiome (molecules, viruses, prokaryotes, uni- and multicellular eukaryotes), and that collect samples using protocols adapted to carrying out the full scope of multi-omics analyses (environmental, genomics, proteomics, metabolomics and phenomics). In this section we include "one-pager step-by-step protocols" that were developed specifically to be carried out on board the research sail boat Tara. These protocols are being published in a dedicated workspace <https://protocols.io/workspaces/mission-microbiomes-atlanteco> on protocols.io and will be described as a whole in a Nature Scientific Data publication (in preparation). These protocols were adapted for use on other research platforms and other initiatives led by AtlantECO (see deliverable D4.9) and will be described in their respective publications.

The second objective of AtlantECO's Handbook was to analyse the various community standards and propose a coherent system of Ocean Microbiome Standard Operating Procedures.

As explained in the previous sections, several protocols targetting the same size- and taxonomic partition of the Ocean microbiome's biological entities may differ in the target filtration volume, membrane porosity or mesh, and preservation method, but nevertheless fall under a single OM-SOP for ease of methodological intercomparison and results integration. This is indeed the case of several protocols used during Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO. For example, protocols "Genomics – S320 – targeting unicellular eukaryotes" and "Genomics – S520-L – targeting unicellular eukaryotes" both fall under the OM-SOP "G2". **Summary Table II** lists all protocols presented in this section, and provides the mapping to the corresponding OM-SOP.

This is operationalised at protocols.io, where each OM-SOP is published as a collection that can branch into many equivalent or derived protocols. These branches can be established with already existing protocols, such as those from project Tara Oceans, or can be created new as we did for Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO. As a legacy, EMBL-EBI will continue to curate the OM-SOPs at protocols.io, and to invite and help other projects to branch in their own protocols into the OM-SOPs, including EMBRC's [EMO-BON](#), EMBL's TRaversing the European Coastline ([TREC](#)) and [EC|BIOcean5D](#).

Summary Table II - AtlantECO protocols

Section	Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO protocol	OM-SOP acronym	OM-SOP size-fraction	OM-SOP target entity
link	Chemistry – SAL – Salinity	E0002	0.002-0.02	environment
link	Chemistry – NUT-1 – Nutrients V1 – Oceano. Rosette	E0002	0.002-0.02	environment
link	Chemistry – NUT-2 – Nutrients V2	E0002	0.002-0.02	environment
link	Chemistry – NUT-3 – Nutrients V3 – Underway	E0002	0.002-0.02	environment
link	Chemistry – DINO – d15Nitrate & d18Oxygen V1	E0002	0.002-0.02	environment
link	Chemistry – DGAS – Dissolved Gasses	E0002	0.002-0.02	environment
link	Chemistry – DO18 – d18Oxygen Isotopes	E0002	0.002-0.02	environment
link	Chemistry – DIC13 – DIC & d13Carbon Isotopes	E0002	0.002-0.02	environment
link	Chemistry – DICTA – DIC & Total Alkalinity	E0002	0.002-0.02	environment
link	Chemistry – MTE-F – Marine Trace Elements – Filtered	E0002	0.002-0.02	environment
link	Chemistry – MTE-T – Marine Trace Elements – Total	E0002	0.002-0.02	environment
link	Chemistry – HG-T – Total Mercury (Hg)	E0002	0.002-0.02	environment
link	Chemistry – HG-M – Methylmercury (MeHg)	E0002	0.002-0.02	environment
link	Chemistry – HG – Particulate Mercury (Hg)	E02	0.2-2	environment
link	Chemistry – NP045 – targeting nanoplastic	E02	0.2-2	environment
link	Chemistry – NP550 – targeting very small microplastic	E2	2-20	environment
link	Chemistry – CP50 – chemistry of microplastics	E20	20-200	environment
link	Chemistry – CP200 – chemistry of microplastics	E200	200-2,000	environment
link	Chemistry – CP330 – chemistry of microplastics	E200	200-2,000	environment

Section	Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO protocol	OM-SOP acronym	OM-SOP size-fraction	OM-SOP target entity
link	Biogeochemistry – PM – Particulate Matter (PN/POC/d13C/d15N)	E02 E2	0.2-2 2-20	prokaryotes eukaryotes
link	Biogeochemistry – PM20 – Particulate Matter (PN/POC/d13C/d15N)	E20	20-200	eukaryotes
link	Biogeochemistry – PM200 – Particulate Matter (PN/POC/d13C/d15N)	E200	200-2,000	eukaryotes
link	Genomics – HC – virus Hi-C sequencing	G002	0.02-0.2	viruses
link	Genomics – S<02 – targeting viruses	G002	0.02-0.2	viruses
link	Genomics – eDNA – targeting large Eukaryotes	G02	>0.2	eukaryotes
link	Genomics – SG – single-organism-genomics pico/nano	G02	0.2-2	prokaryotes
link	Genomics – Aerosols AS – metabarcoding	G02 G2	0.2-2 2-20	prokaryotes
link	Genomics – Aerosols AF – size-fractionated metabarcoding	G02 G2	0.2-2 2-20	prokaryotes
link	Genomics – S025-L – targeting prokaryotes	G02	0.2-2	prokaryotes
link	Genomics – S023 – targeting prokaryotes	G02	0.2-2	prokaryotes
link	Genomics – S320 – targeting unicellular eukaryotes	G2	2-20	eukaryotes
link	Genomics – S520-L – targeting unicellular eukaryotes	G2	2-20	eukaryotes
link	Genomics – S20 – Genomics micro	G20	20-200	eukaryotes
link	Genomics – S20-L – targeting unicellular eukaryotes	G20	20-200	eukaryotes
link	Genomics – S200 – Genomics	G200	200-2,000	eukaryotes
link	Genomics – S200-L – targeting unicellular eukaryotes	G200	200-2,000	eukaryotes
link	Genomics – SP300 – sequencing the plastisphere	G200	200-2,000	eukaryotes
link	Genomics – S680-L (B) – targeting unicellular eukaryotes	G2000	2,000- 20,000	eukaryotes

Section	Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO protocol	OM-SOP acronym	OM-SOP size-fraction	OM-SOP target entity
link	Genomics – S680-L (A) – Genomics	G2000	2,000- 20,000	eukaryotes
link	Proteomics – PT023 – targeting prokaryotes	P02	0.2-2	prokaryotes
link	Proteomics – PT320 – targeting unicellular eukaryotes	P2	2-20	eukaryotes
link	Metabolomics – MB<02 – targeting exometabolites	M0002	0.002-0.02	molecules
link	Metabolomics – MB023 – targeting prokaryotes	M02	0.2-2	prokaryotes
link	Metabolomics – MB320 – targeting unicellular eukaryotes	M2	2-20	eukaryotes
link	Metabolomics – MB20 – targeting unicellular eukaryotes	M20	20-200	eukaryotes
link	Phenomics – HP – pigments (HPLC)	T02 T2 T20	0.2-2 2-20 20-200	prokaryotes eukaryotes
link	Phenomics – FC – flow-cytometry	T002 T02 T2	0.02-0.2 0.2-2 2-20	viruses prokaryotes eukaryotes
link	Phenomics – Aerosols AI – Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)	T02 T2	0.2-2 2-20	prokaryotes eukaryotes
link	Phenomics – SEM – Scanning Electron Microscopy	T02 T2	0.2-2 2-20	prokaryotes eukaryotes
link	Phenomics – FM5 – e-HCFM nano	T2	2-20	eukaryotes
link	Phenomics & Genomics – E5 – single-organism-genomics micro	T2	2-20	eukaryotes
link	Phenomics – 3DEM5 – 3D electron microscopy nano	T2	2-20	eukaryotes
link	Phenomics – FCAM20 – FlowCam 4x	T20	20-200	eukaryotes
link	Phenomics & Genomics – E20 – single-organism-genomics micro	T20	20-200	eukaryotes
link	Phenomics – FM20 – e-HCFM micro	T20	20-200	eukaryotes

Section	Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO protocol	OM-SOP acronym	OM-SOP size-fraction	OM-SOP target entity
link	Phenomics – 3DEM20 – 3D electron microscopy micro	T20	20-200	eukaryotes
link	Phenomics – LU20 – taxonomy	T20	20-200	eukaryotes
link	Phenomics – F200 – ZooScan	T20	20-200	eukaryotes
link	Phenomics & Genomics – E200 – sorting single-organism	T20	20-200	eukaryotes
link	Phenomics – MP300 – Microscopic imaging of the plastisphere	T20	20-200	eukaryotes
link	Phenomics – F680 & F2000 – ZooScan	T2000	2,000- 20,000	eukaryotes
link	Phenomics & Genomics – E2000 – sorting single organisms	T2000	2,000- 20,000	eukaryotes
link	Phenomics & Genomics – E680 & E2000 – sorting single organisms	T2000	2,000- 20,000	eukaryotes

Chemistry – SAL – Salinity

Contact: Gilles Reverdin (reve@locean-ipsl.upmc.fr), LOCEAN, Paris, France

CAUTION – Glass bottles can break

- Separate bottles in the storage box to avoid choc during sailing and transport

Step-by-Step

- Fill the glass bottle, keeping 1 cm of air at the top to allow for water expansion
- Close the glass bottle with the plastic cap insert and the cap
- <!> If cap inserts are not available, secure the outside of the cap with parafilm
- Store in the sample box at room temperature (RT) in the front storage area (F-Store)

Chemistry – NUT-1 – Nutrients V1 – Oceano. Rosette

Contact: Mireille Pujó-Pay, CNRS, LOMIC (puiopay@obs-banyuls.fr)

CAUTION – This protocol is subject to contamination

- **DO NOT smoke** on deck during sampling
- Wear **vinyl gloves**

Step-by-Step

Rinse the syringe:

- 9 Remove the plunger of the syringe and place the Uptidisc on the syringe to prevent the water from flowing out in the next step
- 10 Pour sample water in the syringe to 3/4 full, and place the plunger at the 10 mL mark without pushing it, just to close the syringe
- 11 Shake to rinse the syringe, remove the plunger, and discard the content

Rinse the Uptidisc, vial and cap:

- Fill the syringe with sample water, with the Uptidisc still on
- Place the plunger and push it to discard the first 10 mL
- Fill the 20-ml vial to half with the syringe; Close the vial and shake to rinse it and discard the content (**REPEAT this step a second time**)
- First remove the Uptidisc, then remove the plunger (to avoid rupturing the Uptidisc)
- **DO NOT touch** the end of the Uptidisc with fingers

Collect the sample:

1. Put the Uptidisc back on and fill the syringe again with 50 mL
2. Push the plunger, discard 1 mL and dispense the sample into the vial (leave ~1 cm air)
3. Repeat the previous step if you are collecting duplicate samples
4. **DO NOT wet the neck of the vial or the thread of the cap**; Salt crystals could otherwise form and breach the seal, letting air in, which can contaminate the sample
5. **DO NOT fill to the brim** to allow sample water to expand in the freezer, without breaching the seal and leaking brine
6. Store upright in the sample box at -20°C in the freezer (FRZ) in the front storage area (F-Store)

The same Uptidisc can be used several times, for ex. for 3-4 different samples if the filter does not clog up. Between samples, rinse the Uptidisc with a sterile solution: In marine systems, with 10 mL of saline solution (MilliQ + NaCl 35g/L). In freshwater, river systems, with 10 mL of MilliQ water.

Chemistry – NUT-2 – Nutrients V2

Contact: Mireille Pujo-Pay, CNRS, LOMIC (puiopay@obs-banyuls.fr)

CAUTION – This protocol is subject to contamination

- DO NOT smoke on deck during sampling
- Wear Polyethylene shoulder gloves for trace metals

Step-by-Step

1. Install the Uptidisc filter at the end of the outflow tube
2. Operate the manifold according to instructions given at the beginning of this section
3. Discard the first 10 mL of sample water
4. Fill the 20-ml vial to half with the outflow; Close the vial and shake to rinse it and discard the content (REPEAT this step a second time)
4. Dispense sample water into the vial, leaving ca.1 cm of head space
5. **<!/ DO NOT wet the neck of the vial or the thread of the cap;** Salt crystals could otherwise form and breach the seal, letting air in, which can contaminate the sample
6. **<!/ DO NOT fill to the brim** to allow sample water to expand in the freezer, without breaching the seal and leaking brine
7. Store upright in the sample box at -20°C in the freezer (FRZ) in the front storage area (F-Store)

Chemistry – NUT-3 – Nutrients V3 – Underway

Contact: Gilles Reverdin (gilles.reverdin@locean-ipsl.upmc.fr), LOCEAN, Paris, France

CAUTION – This protocol is subject to contamination

- DO NOT smoke on deck during sampling
- Wear vinyl gloves

Step-by-Step

1. Open the underway outflow valve and discard the first 100 mL
2. Fill the 50-ml bottle to half, close and shake to rinse it and discard the content (REPEAT this step 3x times)
3. Dispense sample water into the bottle up to the base of the neck
4. Close the bottle tightly, using a clamp
5. Pasteurise the sample in an oven at +60°C for 12 hours
6. Tighten the cap as needed using the clamp
7. Store in the sample box at room temperature (RT) in the front storage area (F-Store)

Chemistry – DINO – d15Nitrate & d18Oxygen V1

Contact: Ulisse Cardini (ulisse.cardini@szn.it), Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Napoli, Italy

x2
DUPLICATE

CAUTION – This protocol is subject to contamination

- Use gloves to collect samples

Step-by-step

1. Coordinate with NUT-1 protocol, using the same syringe and uptidisk
2. First remove the Uptidisc, then remove the plunger (to avoid rupturing the Uptidisc)
3. Put the Uptidisc back on and fill the syringe again with 50 mL
4. Push the plunger, discard 1 mL and dispense the sample into the vial (leave ~1 cm air)
5. Repeat the previous step if you are collecting duplicate samples
6. Rinse 3x times the 60-mL Nalgene HDPE bottle with 6 mL of filtered sample water
7. Fill the 60-mL bottle, leaving a headspace and close tightly with the cap
8. Repeat to take duplicate samples
9. Store the bottles upright at -20°C in the freezer (FRZ) in the front storage area (F-Store)

Chemistry – DGAS – Dissolved Gasses

Contact: Ulisse Cardini (ulisse.cardini@szn.it), Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Napoli, Italy

x3
TRIPLICATE

CAUTION – This protocol is subject to contamination and uses toxic substances

- Use gloves to collect the samples & DO NOT smoke on deck during sampling
- Once the venting valve of the Niskin is open, air comes in and gases start to exchange with the seawater sample. To avoid contamination, draw DGAS samples as soon as possible
- Zinc Chloride is toxic; Handle with gloves (see MSDS sheet)
- ZnCl₂ will contaminate Trace Metals samples; DGAS samples and ZnCl₂ must be stowed away before the Trace Metals samples are collected.

Step-by-Step

1. Install a clean silicone tube on the Niskin spigot, and open the spigot
2. Slowly draw sample water directly from the silicone tube, without filtration, just above the opening of the 12-mL Exetainer vial to avoid gas exchange as much as possible
3. Allow abundant overflow
4. Repeat to fill the three replicates and immediately bring the Exetainer vials into the “poison box” on the deck table
5. Dispense 200 µL of ZnCl₂ solution (7 M) on the water meniscus. The ZnCl₂ solution is denser than seawater and will sink
6. Close the exetainer tight, making sure that no bubbles are formed (the meniscus is maintained while closing)
7. Store the Exetainer vials upside-down, in the dark (sample box) at +4°C in the fridge (FRG) in the front storage area (F-Store)

Chemistry – DO18 – d18Oxygen Isotopes

Contact: Gilles Reverdin (gilles.reverdin@locean-ipsl.upmc.fr), LOCEAN, Paris, France

CAUTION – This protocol is subject to contamination

- Use gloves to collect samples

Step-by-step

1. Install a clean silicone tube on the Niskin spigot, and open the spigot
2. Slowly draw sample water directly from the silicone tube, without filtration, just above the opening of the 40-mL bottle to avoid gas exchange as much as possible
3. Allow abundant overflow
4. Close the bottle tightly and secure the cap with parafilm
5. Store in the dark (sample box) at room temperature (RT) in the front storage area (F-Store)

Chemistry – DIC13 – DIC & d13Carbon Isotopes

Contact: Gilles Reverdin (gilles.reverdin@locean-ipsl.upmc.fr), LOCEAN, Paris, France

CAUTION – This protocol is subject to contamination and uses toxic substances

- Use gloves to collect samples & DO NOT smoke on deck during sampling
- Mercuric Chloride (HgCl₂) is toxic; Handle with gloves (see MSDS sheet)
- HgCl₂ will contaminate Mercury samples; DIC13 samples and HgCl₂ must be stowed away before the HG samples are collected

Step-by-step

- Install a clean silicone tube on the Niskin spigot, and open the spigot
- Rinse 3x times the 200-mL glass bottle and its cap using ca. 20 mL of water from the Niskin
- Let the clean silicone tube reach the bottom of the bottle and fill it slowly, avoiding bubbles until it overflows
- Close the Niskin spigot, pinche the silicone tube and slowly remove it from the sample bottle, thus leaving an air space at the top (level with the base of the neck); if this does not work, give the bottle a quick “flick” or use a pipette to get the desired result
- Bring the bottle into the “poison box” on the deck table and add 1000 µL of HgCl₂, using the dedicated pipette
- Close the bottle tightly and secure the cap with parafilm
- Store in the dark (sample box) at room temperature (RT) in the back storage area (B-Store)

Chemistry – DICTA – DIC & Total Alkalinity

Contact: Gilles Reverdin (gilles.reverdin@locean-ipsl.upmc.fr), LOCEAN, Paris, France

CAUTION – This protocol is subject to contamination and uses toxic substances

- Smoking is not allowed on deck during sampling
- Mercuric Chloride (HgCl₂) is toxic; Handle with gloves (see MSDS sheet)
- HgCl₂ will contaminate Mercury samples; DICTA samples and HgCl₂ must be stowed away before the HG samples are collected

Step-by-Step

- Install a clean silicone tube on the Niskin spigot, and open the spigot
- Rinse 3x times the 500-mL sample bottles with ca. 50 mL of sample
- Let the clean silicone tube reach the bottom of the bottle and fill it slowly, avoiding bubbles
- Count in your head the time required to fill the bottle and let the sample water overflow by at least one full volume, counting the filling time once the bottle starts to overflow
- Close the Niskin spigot, pinch the silicone tube and slowly remove it from the sample bottle, thus leaving an air space at the top (0.5 cm below the base of the neck); if this does not work, give the bottle a quick “flick” or use a pipette to get the desired result
- Bring the bottle into the “poison box” on the deck table and add 300 µL of HgCl₂, using the dedicated pipette
- Put three diagonal thin strips of carbon-free Apiezon grease extending 2/3 of the way from the top towards the bottom of the ground portion of the stopper; and Twist it in the neck of the bottle to squeeze the air out of the grease and make a good seal.
- Secure the stopper with a rubber band and invert the bottle gently to disperse the mercuric chloride solution thoroughly.
- Store in the dark (sample box) at room temperature (RT) in the back storage area (B-Store)

Chemistry – MTE-F – Marine Trace Elements – Filtered

Contact: Seth John (sethjohn@usc.edu), USC, California, USA

CAUTION – This protocol is very sensitive to contamination

8. NO smoking on deck during sampling
9. Bottles are already clean and packaged in two plastic bags
10. Wear shoulder-long polyethylene gloves, and short polyethylene gloves on top

Step-by-Step

1. Attach the Supor syringe filter to the end of the line, and flush the filter with 100 mL of seawater
2. Open the, carefully lay down the cap upside-down
<!-- far to the back of the hood (so that you don't have to reach over it with your sleeves). -->
3. Rinse the 125-mL sample bottle twice with 20-30 mL of seawater, capping each time and shaking. Carefully pour off the rinse solution into the plastic beaker, make sure to pour onto the sides of the beaker so that no water splashes back into the bottle.
<!-- Carefully attach the sample tubing on its hook inside the flow bench, so that the filter does not touch anything and become contaminated. -->
4. Fill the bottle with sample, and return the bottle to the plastic bags.
5. Repeat with the other samples.

Chemistry – MTE-T – Marine Trace Elements – Total

Contact: Seth John (sethjohn@usc.edu), USC, California, USA

CAUTION – This protocol is extremely sensitive to contamination

11. DO NOT smoke on deck during sampling
12. Bottles are already clean and packaged in two plastic bags
13. Wear shoulder-long polyethylene gloves, and short polyethylene gloves on top

Step-by-Step

1. Before filling each sample bottle, flush ~500 mL of seawater through the lines to wash out any possible contamination.
2. Open up your bottle, carefully laying the cap upside-down far to the back of the hood (so that you don't have to reach over it with your sleeves).
3. Rinse the bottle twice with 20-30 mL of seawater, capping each time and shaking. Carefully pour off the rinse solution into plastic beaker, make sure to pour onto the sides of the beaker so that no water splashes back into the bottle. While you are rinsing, carefully loop the sample tubing onto a hook inside the flow bench, so that the filter does not touch anything and become contaminated.
4. Fill the bottle with sample, and return the bottle to the plastic bags.
5. Repeat with the other samples.

Chemistry – HG-T – Total Mercury (Hg)

Contact: Lars-Eric Heimbürger (lars-eric.heimburger@mio.osupytheas.fr), MIO, Marseille, France

CAUTION – This protocol is sensitive to mercury contamination

14. DO NOT smoke on deck during sampling
15. DO NOT use mercuric chloride on deck during sampling
16. HG samples MUST BE SAMPLED AFTER both the HgCl₂ solution and the DICTA & DIC13 samples are stowed away; Change gloves before sampling for HG
17. Bottles are already clean
18. Wear gloves when opening the bag to label the bottle before the station

Step-by-Step

1. Uncap the sampling bottle and place the cap on a clean surface
2. Open the manifold valve and discard the first 10 mL
3. Rinse 3x times the 40-mL glass bottle with ca. 5 mL the sample water
4. Fill the bottle slowly, avoiding bubbles, until the **bottle is filled to the very top**
5. Close the sample bottle cap very tight, rinse the outside with fresh water and dry with a cloth
6. Store in the sample box at room temperature (RT) in the front storage area (F-Store)

Chemistry – HG-M – Methylmercury (MeHg)

Contact: Lars-Eric Heimbürger (lars-eric.heimburger@mio.osupytheas.fr), MIO, Marseille, France

CAUTION – This protocol is very sensitive to contamination

19. Bottles are already clean and packaged in one plastic bag
20. Wear gloves when opening the bag to label the bottle before the station
21. DO NOT smoke on deck during sampling
22. DO NOT use mercuric chloride on deck during sampling
23. HG samples MUST BE SAMPLED AFTER both the HgCl_2 solution and the DICTA & DIC13 samples are stowed away; Change gloves before sampling for HG

Step-by-Step

- Uncap the sampling bottle and place the cap in its plastic bag
- Install a clean silicone tube on the Niskin spigot, and open the spigot
- Rinse 3x times the 125-mL PET bottle with the sample water
- Let the clean silicone tube reach the bottom of the bottle and fill it slowly, avoiding bubbles
- Fill the bottle and remove the tube while still flowing so that the **bottle is filled to the very top**
- Bring the bottle in the W-Lab fume-hood and add 1 mL of HCL using the concentrated stock solution and pipette in the chemical box outside the W-Lab
- Close the sample bottle cap very tight, rinse the outside with fresh water and dry with a cloth
- Place the bottle in the plastic bag and close it
- Store in the sample box at room temperature (RT) in the front storage area (F-Store)

Chemistry – HG – Particulate Mercury (Hg)

Contact: Lars-Eric Heimbürger (lars-eric.heimburger@mio.osupytheas.fr), MIO, Marseille, France

Natalia Torres-Rodriguez (natalia.torres-rodriguez@mio.osupytheas.fr), MIO, Marseille, France

Combusted

GF/F
0.7 µm
47 mm
+440 °C

FRZ
-20

DRY
+60
12h

RT
+40
+10

CAUTION – This protocol is moderately sensitive to mercury contamination

Step-by-Step

1. Make sure that there are aluminium envelope containing the pre-combusted 47-mm GFF filters in the clean box on the top shelf
2. Open the middle filter holder and rinse the inside generously with **FSW**
3. Using two clean tweezers, place **a Dacron pre-filters** and the pre-combusted 47-mm GFF filter, and close the filter holder
4. Wipe the intake (sample side) tube with **EtOH** in your glove and then rinse with **MQW**, and place the tube in the 10-L sample carboy
5. Open the bleeding valve before starting the pump
6. Start the pump and start the timer of the filtration line
7. Close the bleeding valves once sample water comes out without air
8. Filter 10L of sample material for 30 min or maximum 60 min until the filter is clogged and water does not flow through
9. Stop the pump and the timer
10. Proceed to “end the filtration” as described above
11. Using two clean tweezers, fold the filter in two with the sample material inside, and place it inside its aluminium foil envelope
12. Place the aluminium envelope in its plastic bag and store it temporarily in the ice box in the fume hood
13. Dry the filter in the oven at +60°C for 12-24h and store in the sample box at room temperature (RT) in the front storage area (F-Store)

<!/ Note on the logsheet the filtration time and volume seawater filtered

Chemistry – NP045 – targeting nanoplastic

Contact: Alexandra ter Halle (ter-halle@chimie.ups-tlse.fr) Université Paul Sabatier, Toulouse, France

Chemistry – NP550 – targeting very small microplastic

Contact: Alexandra ter Halle (ter-halle@chimie.ups-tlse.fr) Université Paul Sabatier, Toulouse, France

Rinse filter, dry and store / lab will re-condition

CAUTION – This protocol is very sensitive to contamination from nano- and micro-plastics

Step-by-Step

1. Before each filtration, run **MQW** through the system, and pump air until it is all purged.
2. Rinse the tweezers with alcohol and then **MQW**, and open the filter holders.
3. Open the aluminium foil, place the light coloured 47-mm inox filter (50 μm) in the first filter holder. Place the darker 47-mm inox filter in the second filter holder. Place the 25-mm GF/F filter in the third one. Be sure to prevent the opened filter holder to touch any surface. Be sure the black joint is placed properly on the top.
4. Wipe the intake (sample side) tube with **EtOH** in your glove and then rinse with **MQW**, and insert it in the small opening of the carboy.
5. Start the filtration at a speed of 70 to 80. If the filter is clogged, the debit of water slows down. To prevent generation of leaks, lower the speed of the pump to 30. If the debit is too slow, the filter is saturated. Stop the filtration and record how much water was filtered.
6. Purge the system, be sure all water is gone.
7. Rinse the tweezers with alcohol and then **MQW** and recover the first filter (50 μm inox); rinse it with water; dry it on a clean piece of paper. Place it in an aluminium foil with all the 50μm grids. Do not bend. They will be calcinated and re-used in the next campaign.
8. Rinse the tweezers with alcohol and then **MQW**, and recover the next filter (5 μm inox grid, darker). Bend it in 4 along one direction. Open the 20 ml glass vial. Place the cap face down in a clean surface (aluminium foil). Place it in the 20 ml glass vial with a whit cap.
9. Rinse the tweezers with alcohol and then **MQW**, and recover the next filter (GF/F, white). Bend it in 4 along one direction. Open the 4 ml glass vial. Place the cap face down in a clean surface (aluminium foil). Place it in the 4 ml glass vial with a black cap.
10. Store both vials at -20°C in the freezer (FRZ) in the front storage area (F-Store).

Chemistry – CP50 – chemistry of microplastics

Contact: Jean-François Ghiglione, CNRS, LOMIC (ghiglione@obs-banyuls.fr)

Step-by-Step

1. Thoroughly rinse one or two 47-mm filter holders and cups with **MQW**
2. Place a 47-mm diameter 50-µm stainless steel filter in the “500-mL stericup” system
3. Gently but thoroughly mix the 2-L bottle and pour ca. 100 mL in the filtration cup
4. Suck the water through using the manual vacuum pump
5. Gradually add more volume, always mixing the 2-L bottle before pouring; Not too much at a time in case the filter clogs
6. Thoroughly rinse the cups with **MQW**, using a little suction to drain; Repeat as needed
7. Remove the filter and package it in a square of aluminium foil
8. Thoroughly rinse the 47mm filter holders, cups, red-cap bottles and the cylinder with **FRW**; re-assemble the stericup system
9. Temporarily place the sample in the oven at +60°C for 12-24h
10. Place the sample in its Whirlpack (match the two barcode stickers)
11. Store in the dedicated box at room temperature (RT) in the front storage area (F-Store)

Chemistry – CP200 – chemistry of microplastics

Contact: Jean-François Ghiglione, CNRS, LOMIC (ghiglione@obs-banyuls.fr)

Step-by-Step

1. Thoroughly rinse one or two 47-mm filter holders and cups with **MQW**
2. Place a 47-mm diameter 200-µm stainless steel filter in the “500-mL stericup” system
3. Gently but thoroughly mix one or two 250-mL glass jar(s) and pour sample in the filtration cup
4. Suck the water through using the manual vacuum pump
5. Gradually add more volume, always mixing the 250-mL glass jar before pouring; Not too much at a time in case the filter clogs
6. Thoroughly rinse the cups with **MQW**, using a little suction to drain; Repeat as needed
7. Remove the filter and package it in a square of aluminium foil
8. Thoroughly rinse the 47mm filter holders, cups, red-cap bottles and the cylinder with **FRW**; re-assemble the stericup system
9. Temporarily place the sample in the oven at +60°C for 12-24h
10. Place the sample in its Whirlpack (match the two barcode stickers)
11. Store in the dedicated box at room temperature (RT) in the front storage area (F-Store)

Chemistry – CP330 – chemistry of microplastics

Contact: Jean-François Ghiglione, CNRS, LOMIC (ghiglione@obs-banyuls.fr)

Once all pieces are sorted and processed for protocols **SP300** and **MP300**, pour all remaining material from the first 2-L glass bottle into the second one. All that material should be collected on one or maximum two 47-mm diameter stainless steel filter. If there is too much material, concentrate it in a 20-µm stainless steel sieve and package it in a Whirlpack.

Step-by-Step

1. Thoroughly rinse one or two 47-mm filter holders and cups with **MQW**
2. Place a 47-mm diameter 200-µm stainless steel filter in the “500-mL stericup” system
3. Gently but thoroughly mix the 2-L bottle and pour ca. 100 mL in the filtration cup
4. Suck the water through using the manual vacuum pump
5. Gradually add more volume, always mixing the 2-L bottle before pouring; Not too much at a time in case the filter clogs
6. Thoroughly rinse the cups with **MQW**, using a little suction to drain; Repeat as needed
7. Remove the filter and package it in a square of aluminium foil
8. Thoroughly rinse the 47mm filter holders, cups, red-cap bottles and the cylinder with **FRW**; re-assemble the stericup system
9. Temporarily place the sample in the oven at +60°C for 12-24h
10. Place the sample in its Whirlpack (match the two barcode stickers)

Store in the dedicated box at room temperature (RT) in the front storage area (F-Store)

BioGeoChemistry – PM – Particulate Matter (PN/POC/d13C/d15N)

Contact: Daniela Banaru (Daniela.BANARU@univ-amu.fr), MIO, Marseille, France

CAUTION – This protocol is sensitive to carbon contamination

This protocol uses pre-combusted and pre-weighed GF/F filters

Step-by-Step

1. Make sure that there are aluminium envelope containing the pre-combusted 47-mm GFF filters in the clean box on the top shelf
2. Open the middle filter holder and rinse the inside generously with **FSW**
3. Using two clean tweezers, place **a Dacron pre-filters** and the pre-combusted 47-mm GFF filter, and close the filter holder
4. Wipe the intake (sample side) tube with **EtOH** in your glove and then rinse with **MQW**, and place the tube in the 10-L sample carboy
5. Open the bleeding valve before starting the pump
6. Start the pump and start the timer of the filtration line
7. Close the bleeding valves once sample water comes out without air
8. Filter 8L of sample material for 30 min or maximum 60 min until the filter is clogged and water does not flow through
9. Stop the pump and the timer; note the time and filtered volume on the logsheet
10. Proceed to “end the filtration” as described above
11. Using two clean tweezers, fold the filter in two with the sample material inside, and place it inside its aluminium foil envelope
12. Place the aluminium envelope in its plastic bag and store it temporarily in the ice box in the fume hood
13. Dry the filter in the oven at +60°C for 12-24h and store in the sample box at room temperature (RT) in the front storage area (F-Store)

<!/ Note on the logsheet the filtration time and volume seawater filtered

BioGeoChemistry – PM₂₀ – Particulate Matter (PN/POC/d13C/d15N)

Contact: Daniela Banaru (Daniela.BANARU@univ-amu.fr), MIO, Marseille, France

CAUTION – This protocol is sensitive to carbon contamination

This protocol uses pre-combusted and pre-weighed GF/F filters

Step-by-Step

1. Make sure that there are aluminium envelope containing the pre-combusted 47-mm GFF filters in the clean box on the top shelf
2. Using two clean tweezers, place a Dacron pre-filter and the pre-combusted 47-mm GFF filter, and close the filter holder
3. Gently, but thoroughly mix the content of the 250-mL glass jar and pour slowly and progressively on the membrane until all the matter is collected
4. Using two clean tweezers, fold the filter in two with the sample material inside, and place it inside its aluminium foil envelope
5. Place the aluminium envelope in its plastic bag and store it temporarily in the ice box in the fume hood
6. Dry the filter in the oven at +60°C for 12-24h and store in the sample box at room temperature (RT) in the front storage area (F-Store)

<!/ Note on the logsheet the filtration time and volume seawater filtered

BioGeoChemistry – PM200 – Particulate Matter (PN/POC/d13C/d15N)

Contact: Daniela Banaru (Daniela.BANARU@univ-amu.fr), MIO, Marseille, France

CAUTION – This protocol is sensitive to carbon contamination

This protocol uses pre-combusted and pre-weighed GF/F filters

Step-by-Step

1. Make sure that there are aluminium envelope containing the pre-combusted 47-mm GFF filters in the clean box on the top shelf
2. Using two clean tweezers, place a Dacron pre-filter and the pre-combusted 47-mm GFF filter, and close the filter holder
3. Gently, but thoroughly mix the content of the 250-mL glass jar and pour slowly and progressively on the membrane until all the matter is collected
4. You may filter a second 250-mL glass jar if there is very little material
5. Using two clean tweezers, fold the filter in two with the sample material inside, and place it inside its aluminium foil envelope
6. Place the aluminium envelope in its plastic bag and store it temporarily in the ice box in the fume hood
7. Dry the filter in the oven at +60°C for 12-24h and store in the sample box at room temperature (RT) in the front storage area (F-Store)

<!> **Note on the logsheet** the filtration time and volume seawater filtered

Genomics – HC – virus Hi-C sequencing

Contact: Matthew Sullivan, Ohio State University, USA (mbsulli@gmail.com)

x4
REPLICATES

Step-by-Step

1. Dispense 1.5 mL of whole seawater into a 2-mL cryotube (grey cap-insert).
2. Close the cryotube and mix gently by inversion
3. Temporarily place in the **RED** thermos container for max 15 minutes
4. Store in Liquid Nitrogen dewar #2 in the W-Lab.

Genomics – S<02 – targeting viruses

Contact: Matthew Sullivan, Ohio State University, USA (mbsulli@gmail.com)

<After 1-24 hours>

- Place Dacron pre-filters on all the tripods, then a 0.8- μm filters on the tripods, and close all tripods tightly with the key
- Wipe the intake tubes with **EtOH** with your glove and then rinse with **FSW**, and place the tubes in their respective 20-L filtrate carboys
- Open all bleeding valves before starting the pumps
- Start the pumps and start the timer for each filtration line
- Close the bleeding valves once sample water comes out without air

When all water went through the filters OR <!-- no longer than 60 minutes

- Open the pump head to pause pumping on the line, keep the pump running and stop the timer
- Leave the intake (filtrate side) tube in its carboy, **OR <!-- lift it above the water level** if some sample remains in the carboy
- **<!-- Cell damage and DNA & RNA degradation happens when the material dries on the filter**; Do not proceed to end a filtration unless you are ready to collect the filter; better wait that all filtrations are finished before proceeding to end a filtration
- Proceed to end the filtration (see above)
- Place the filters in their respective 5-mL cryotube
- Store at +4°C in the Fridge (FRG) in the front storage area (F-Store)

Genomics – eDNA – targeting large Eukaryotes

Contact: Naiara Rodríguez-Ezpeleta (nrodriguez@azti.es), AZTI, Spain

CAUTION –
Wear gloves

Step-by-Step

1. Softly shake the water bottles two or three times to homogenise the sample
2. Place the tube inside the bottle and switch on the pump to make some clean water pass through.
3. Stop the pump and place the Sterivex 0.45- μ m filter at the exit of the tube.
4. Start the timer
5. Before stopping the filtration, it is necessary that the tube and sterivex filter are empty.
6. Stop the timer
7. Remove the sterivex filter, put the 2 types of caps and place in the labelled bag. Store at -80 °C (or -20 °C for a shorter period)
8. Write the filtration time on the logsheet

<!/ Note on the logsheet the filtration time and volume seawater filtered

Genetics – SG – single-organism-genomics pico/nano

Contact:

x3
TRIPLICATE

CAUTION – Glycine Betaine is not a toxic substance

- Wear gloves, handle with care, and read the safety sheet (MSDS)
- The pre-aliquoted cryotubes are kept at +4°C in the fridge (FRG) in the front storage area (F-Store)

Step-by-Step

1. Dispense 4 mL of whole seawater into a 5-mL cryotube (star-shaped cap) pre-aliquoted with 600 µL of 48% Glycine Betaine.
2. Close the cryotube and mix gently by inversion
3. Temporarily place in the **RED** thermos container for max 15 minutes
4. Store in Liquid Nitrogen dewar #1 in the W-Lab

Genomics – Aerosols AS – metabarcoding

Contact: Michel Flores, Weizmann Institute (flores@weizmann.ac.il)

Put on gloves and wash your gloves/hands with **EtOH**

Step-by-Step

1. The AS filter is in the **YELLOW** filter holder
2. Open the filter holder and place the “o-ring” sideways in the black stage.
3. Fold the 47-mm-diameter 0.45-µm PVDF filter in two and again in two, and put it in the cryotube.
4. Place a new PVDF filter in the filter holder and close.
5. Store the cryotube in liquid nitrogen (Dewar #3) in the W-Lab

Genomics – Aerosols AF – size-fractionated metabarcoding

Contact: Michel Flores, Weizmann Institute (flores@weizmann.ac.il)

Put on gloves and wash your gloves/hands with **EtOH**

Step-by-Step

1. The five AF filters are in the **RED** “impactor” filter holder
2. Setup your working space in the fumehood with (1) the box of 47mm filters, (2) the box of 70 mm filters, (3) the box of square aluminium foils, (4) a marker pen, and (5) the pre-labelled Whirlpack. Place two square aluminium foils flat on the working surface, i.e. one for the first filter and one to pile-up the impactor stages (see next steps).
3. Open and slowly lift vertically the cap of the impactor, exposing the five stainless steel “stages” of the “impactor”. The stages are labelled in descending order from 4 (topmost) to 0 (bottom-most).
4. Take the filter on “stage 4” and put it on a clean aluminium foil, fold the filter in two and again in two. Fold each corner of the foil inwards to completely wrap the filter, flip it up-side down, write “4” on the foil, and put into the Whirlpack.
5. Put “stage 4” filter holder on the second clean aluminium foil and place a new square aluminium foil on the working space for the next filter. Repeat for stages 3 to 0. The filters are therefore labelled in descending order from 4 (topmost) to 0 (bottom-most). Note that the filters on stages 4 to 1 are 47 mm in diameter, whereas the filter on stage 0 is 70 mm in diameter.
6. Place sticker on sterile bag and place in -20C freezer.
7. Put new filters in the impactor, starting with the large filter on stage 0. The new filters for stages 1-4 are in an aluminium package (one package contains 4 filters). Place one filter on each stage as you reassemble the impactor.
8. Close the impactor.
9. Store the Whirlpack in the “aerosols sample box” at room temperature (RT) in the F-Store

Genomics – S025-L – targeting prokaryotes

Contact: Partick Wincker, CEA, Genoscope, France (pwincker@genoscope.cns.fr)

CAUTION – This protocol uses toxic substances

Read the nucleoprotect MSDS

Wear gloves and work in the fume hood

Step-by-Step

1. Proceed to filter 50L of decknet filtrate on the filtration ramp #5
2. Once the filtration is finished, fold the filter in half with two dissecting tweezers and then fold it in half again lengthwise without touching the sample with the tweezers and without "crushing" the filter too much.
3. Insert the filter into a 15ml Falcon screw cap tube.
4. "Sink" the filter into the bottom of the tube.
5. Add 15 ml Nucleoprotect.
6. Mix by inversion 3 times.
7. Check that the entire filter is fully immersed in the buffer.
8. Store the tube at -20 °C (the tube can remain at room temperature for a few hours).

Genomics – S023 – targeting prokaryotes

Contact: Partick Wincker, CEA, Genoscope, France (pwincker@genoscope.cns.fr)

Genomics – S320 – targeting unicellular eukaryotes

Step-by-Step:

- Humidify all filter holders generously with **FSW**
- Place Dacron pre-filters on all the tripods, then a 3- μm filters on the first tripods of each line, and a 0.2- μm filter on the second ones, and close all tripods tightly with the key
- Wipe the intake (sample side) and outflow (filtrate side) tubes with **EtOH** in your glove and then rinse with **FSW**, and place the tubes in their respective 10-L, 20-L or 50-L carboys
- Open all bleeding valves before starting the pumps
- Start the pumps and start the timer for each filtration line
- Close the bleeding valves once sample water comes out without air

When all water went through the filters OR <!-- no longer than 15 minutes

- Open the pump head to pause pumping on the line, keep the pump running and stop the timer
- Leave the intake (sample side) tube in its carboy, **OR <!-- lift it above the water level** if some sample remains in the carboy
- **<!-- Cell damage and DNA & RNA degradation happens when the material dries on the filter**; Do not proceed to end a filtration unless you are ready to collect the filter; better wait that all filtrations are finished before proceeding to end a filtration
- Proceed to end the filtration (see above)
- Place the filters in their respective 5-mL cryotube
- Store immediately in Liquid nitrogen (Dewar #1)

When all filtrations are ended AND <!-- all samples are stored in liquid nitrogen

- If applicable, measure the volume of sample left in any of the carboys
- **<!-- Note on the logsheet** the filtration time and volume of filtrate obtained from all filtrations
- Add 1 mL of the stock solution of Iron Chloride (1 g FeCl_3 in 50 mL ultrapure water) to each filtrate so that the final concentration is 1 mg/L of filtrate.
- Shake vigorously the 20-L carboy and leave it to incubate 1-24 hours in the W-Lab

Genomics – S520-L – targeting unicellular eukaryotes

Contact: Partick Wincker, CEA, Genoscope, France (pwincker@genoscope.cns.fr)

CAUTION – This protocol uses toxic substances

- Read the nucleoprotect MSDS
- Wear gloves and work in the fume hood

Step-by-Step

1. Using two dissecting tweezers, fold the filter in half without touching the sample with the tweezers and without "crushing" the filter too much.
2. Insert the filter into a 5ml Falcon tube.
3. Add 5 ml Nucleoprotect.
4. Mix by inversion 3 times.
5. Check that the entire filter is fully submerged in the buffer.
6. Store the tube at -20 °C (the tube may remain at room temperature for a few hours).

Genomics – S20 – Genomics micro

Contact: Julie Poulin, Genoscope (poulain@genoscope.cns.fr)

CAUTION – This protocol is sensitive to RNA degradation - 15 min max

Step-by-Step

- Thoroughly rinse one 47-mm filter holder and cup with **MQW**
 - Place a 10- μ m PC filter on the filter holder and place the cup on top
 - Gently but thoroughly mix the 250-mL glass bottles and pour ca. 100 mL in the filtration cup
 - Switch on the suction; Gradually add more volume, always mixing the glass bottle before pouring; Not too much at a time in case the filter clogs
 - **<!/ Do not exceed 15 minutes** for the filtrations; keep the remaining volume in the glass bottles to measure the unfiltered volume in a graduated cylinder
 - Switch off the suction as soon as the filter gets dry
1. Thoroughly rinse the cup with **FSW**, using a little suction to drain; Repeat as needed and remove the cup
 2. Using two dissecting tweezers, fold the filter in half without touching the sample with the tweezers and without "crushing" the filter too much.
- Package it in a 5-mL cryotube and immediately store the cryotube in liquid nitrogen Dewar #1
 - **<!/ write on the logsheet the total volume filtered**
 - Thoroughly rinse the 47mm filter holder, cup and cylinders with **FRW**; re-assemble the filter holders and cups; rinse with **EtOH**

Genomics – S20-L – targeting unicellular eukaryotes

Contact: Partick Wincker, CEA, Genoscope, France (pwincker@genoscope.cns.fr)

CAUTION – This protocol uses toxic substances

- Read the nucleoprotect MSDS
- Wear gloves and work in the fume hood

Step-by-Step

1. Thoroughly rinse one 47-mm filter holder and cup with **MQW**
2. Place a 10-µm PC filter on the filter holder and place the cup on top
3. Gently but thoroughly mix the 250-mL glass bottles and pour ca. 100 mL in the filtration cup
4. Switch on the suction; Gradually add more volume, always mixing the glass bottle before pouring; Not too much at a time in case the filter clogs
5. **<!/ Do not exceed 15 minutes** for the filtrations; keep the remaining volume in the glass bottles to measure the unfiltered volume in a graduated cylinder
6. Switch off the suction as soon as the filter gets dry
7. Thoroughly rinse the cup with **FSW**, using a little suction to drain; Repeat as needed and remove the cup
8. Using two dissecting tweezers, fold the filter in half without touching the sample with the tweezers and without "crushing" the filter too much.
9. Insert the filter into a 5-ml Falcon tube, add 5 ml of Nucleoprotect; mix by inversion 3 times.
10. Check that the entire filter is fully submerged in the buffer and store the tube at -20 °C.
11. **<!/ write on the logsheet the total volume filtered**
12. Thoroughly rinse the 47mm filter holder, cup and cylinders with **FRW**; re-assemble the filter holders and cups; rinse with **EtOH**

Genomics – S200 – Genomics

Contact: Julie Poulain, Genoscope (poulain@genoscope.cns.fr)

Step-by-Step

- Thoroughly rinse one 47-mm filter holder and cup with **MQW**
- Place a 10- μ m PC filter on the filter holder and place the cup on top
- Gently but thoroughly mix the 250-mL glass bottles and pour ca. 50 mL in the filtration cup
- Switch on the suction; Gradually add more volume, always mixing the glass bottle before pouring; Not too much at a time in case the filter clogs
- **<!/ Do not exceed 15 minutes** for the filtrations; keep the remaining volume in the glass bottles to measure the unfiltered volume in a graduated cylinder
- Switch off the suction as soon as the filter gets dry
- 3. Thoroughly rinse the cup with **FSW**, using a little suction to drain; Repeat as needed and remove the cup
- 4. Using two dissecting tweezers, fold the filter in half without touching the sample with the tweezers and without "crushing" the filter too much.
- Package it in a 5-mL cryotube and immediately store the cryotube in liquid nitrogen Dewar #1
- **<!/ write on the logsheet the total volume filtered**
- Thoroughly rinse the 47mm filter holder, cup and cylinders with **FRW**; re-assemble the filter holders and cups; rinse with **EtOH**

Genomics – S200-L – targeting unicellular eukaryotes

Contact: Partick Wincker, CEA, Genoscope, France (pwincker@genoscope.cns.fr)

CAUTION – This protocol uses toxic substances

- Read the nucleoprotect MSDS
- Wear gloves and work in the fume hood

Step-by-Step

1. Thoroughly rinse one 47-mm filter holder and cup with **MQW**
2. Place a 10-µm PC filter on the filter holder and place the cup on top
3. Gently but thoroughly mix the 250-mL glass bottles and pour ca. 50 mL in the filtration cup
4. Switch on the suction; Gradually add more volume, always mixing the glass bottle before pouring; Not too much at a time in case the filter clogs
5. **<!/ Do not exceed 15 minutes** for the filtrations; keep the remaining volume in the glass bottles to measure the unfiltered volume in a graduated cylinder
6. Switch off the suction as soon as the filter gets dry
7. Thoroughly rinse the cup with **FSW**, using a little suction to drain; Repeat as needed and remove the cup
8. Using two dissecting tweezers, fold the filter in half without touching the sample with the tweezers and without "crushing" the filter too much.
9. Insert the filter into a 5-ml Falcon tube, add 5 ml of Nucleoprotect; mix by inversion 3 times.
10. Check that the entire filter is fully submerged in the buffer and store the tube at -20 °C.
11. **<!/ write on the logsheet the total volume filtered**
12. Thoroughly rinse the 47mm filter holder, cup and cylinders with **FRW**; re-assemble the filter holders and cups; rinse with **EtOH**

Genomics – SP300 – sequencing the plastisphere

Contact: Jean-François Ghiglione, CNRS, LOMIC (ghiglione@obs-banyuls.fr)

Step-by-Step

Small pieces of plastic

1. Package the entire piece in a 2-mL cryotube
2. Label the cryotube and the logsheet with a barcode sticker
3. Temporarily store the cryotube in the S-Lab freezer

Large pieces of plastic

1. Carefully hold the piece with the clean tweezer and cut it with the clean scissor into two parts, a large (2/3 or more) and a small (1/3 or less)
2. Package the larger part in a 2-mL cryotube
3. Label the cryotube and the logsheet with a barcode sticker
4. Temporarily store the cryotube in the S-Lab freezer
5. Keep the smaller part for protocol **MP300**

Genomics – S680-L (B) – targeting unicellular eukaryotes

Contact: Partick Wincker, CEA, Genoscope, France (pwincker@genoscope.cns.fr)

CAUTION – This protocol uses toxic substances

- Read the nucleoprotect MSDS
- Wear gloves and work in the fume hood

Step-by-Step

1. Thoroughly rinse one 47-mm filter holder and cup with **MQW**
2. Place a 10-µm PC filter on the filter holder and place the cup on top
3. Gently but thoroughly mix the 250-mL glass bottles and pour ca. 100 mL in the filtration cup
4. Switch on the suction; Gradually add more volume, always mixing the glass bottle before pouring; Not too much at a time in case the filter clogs
5. **<!/ Do not exceed 15 minutes** for the filtrations; keep the remaining volume in the glass bottles to measure the unfiltered volume in a graduated cylinder
6. Switch off the suction as soon as the filter gets dry
7. Thoroughly rinse the cup with **FSW**, using a little suction to drain; Repeat as needed and remove the cup
8. Using two dissecting tweezers, fold the filter in half without touching the sample with the tweezers and without "crushing" the filter too much.
9. Insert the filter into a 5-ml Falcon tube, add 5 ml of Nucleoprotect; mix by inversion 3 times.
10. Check that the entire filter is fully submerged in the buffer and store the tube at -20 °C.
11. **<!/ write on the logsheet the total volume filtered**
12. Thoroughly rinse the 47mm filter holder, cup and cylinders with **FRW**; re-assemble the filter holders and cups; rinse with **EtOH**

Genomics – S680-L (A) – Genomics

Contact: Partick Wincker, CEA, Genoscope, France (pwincker@genoscope.cns.fr)

Step-by-Step

1. Thoroughly rinse the 200- μ m sieve and three 250-mL red-cap bottles with **MQW**
2. Gently but thoroughly mix the 2-L bottle and pour 200 mL in each 250-mL red-cap bottle
3. **Strainer #1**
 - a. Place the sterile 100- μ m strainer on its holder (modified 50-mL Falcon) using clean tweezers, and cut its “wing” with clean scissors
 - b. Gently but thoroughly mix the first 250-mL red-cap bottle and pour its content into the 200- μ m sieve; Thoroughly rinse the sieve with **FSW**
 - c. Gather all material on the “spout” side of the sieve using the **FSW** squeeze bottle
 - d. Wash all material off the sieve into the strainer using the **FSW** squeeze bottle
 - e. **<!/ Do not fill more than half the strainer with material**
 - If that limit is reached with very little material still in the 200- μ m sieve, continue to wash-off the material in Strainer #1
 - If that limit is reached with an equivalent quantity of material still in the 200- μ m sieve, keep the material in the sieve for Strainer #2
 - If only ca. $\frac{1}{4}$ of Strainer #1 is full, repeat steps 3b-3e with the second 250-mL red-cap bottle, and eventually with the third 250-mL red-cap bottle
 - f. Using clean tweezers, place the strainer in the 6-petri-plate, and dispense 10 mL of Nucleoprotect into the strainer
4. **Strainer #2:** repeat step 3 with a second strainer if needed
5. **<!/ Do not use more than two strainers**
6. **<!/ Try not to leave any material in the 200- μ m sieve**, i.e. do not sieve a second or third 250-mL red-cap bottle unless you will be able to collect all its material in the strainers
7. **<!/ Write on the logsheet** the total volume filtered on the strainer(s), e.g. “500 mL”
8. Cover the two wells (6-petri-plate) that contain the strainers with and adhesive aluminium foil, i.e. covering half the 6-petri-plate
9. Store the 6-petri-plate at +4°C in the Fridge until it is used for 2 nets; then store at -20°C in the Freezer
10. Thoroughly rinse the 200- μ m sieve and the red-cap bottles with **FRW** and then with **EtOH**

IF THERE IS TOO MUCH MATERIAL >> 15mL or 2x 5mL

Proteomics – PT023 – targeting prokaryotes

Contact: Mak Saito, Woods Hole Oceanography Institute, USA (msaito@whoi.edu)

Proteomics – PT320 – targeting unicellular eukaryotes

Step-by-Step:

1. Humidify all filter holders generously with **FSW**
2. Place Dacron pre-filters on all the tripods, then a 3- μ m filters on the first tripods of each line, and a 0.2- μ m filter on the second ones, and close all tripods tightly with the key
3. Wipe the intake (sample side) and outflow (filtrate side) tubes with **EtOH** in your glove and then rinse with **FSW**, and place the tubes in their respective 10-L, 20-L or 50-L carboys
4. Open all bleeding valves before starting the pumps
5. Start the pumps and start the timer for each filtration line
6. Close the bleeding valves once sample water comes out without air
7. *<!-- if 10-L carboys are used to collect the filtrate, either let filtrate overflow once full, or close the carboy with its cap and collect the **FSW** filtrate in a dedicated carboy used for rinsing*

When all water went through the filters OR <!-- no longer than 60 minutes

8. Open the pump head to pause pumping on the line, and keep the pump running
9. Leave the intake (sample side) tube in its carboy, ***OR <!-- lift it above the water level*** if some sample remains in the carboy
10. ***<!-- Cell damage and degradation happens when the material dries on the filter;*** Do not proceed to end a filtration unless you are ready to collect the filter; better wait that all filtrations are finished before proceeding to end a filtration
11. Proceed to end the filtration (see above)
12. Place the filters in their respective 5-mL cryotube
13. Store immediately in Liquid nitrogen (Dewar #1)
14. If applicable, measure the volume of sample left in any of the carboys

<!-- Note on the logsheet the filtration time and volume of filtrate obtained from all filtrations

Metabolomics – MB<02 – targeting exometabolites

Contact: Georg Pohnert (georg.pohnert@uni-jena.de) University of Jena, Germany

Metabolomics – MB023 – targeting prokaryotes

Contact: Georg Pohnert (georg.pohnert@uni-jena.de) University of Jena, Germany

Metabolomics – MB320 – targeting unicellular eukaryotes

Contact: Georg Pohnert (georg.pohnert@uni-jena.de) University of Jena, Germany

CAUTION – This protocol is very sensitive to contamination from the skin

- Wear *Nitrile gloves* at all time
- Always clean tweezers with EtOH and then MilliQ water before use

Step-by-Step

Immediately before starting the filtration:

1. Place the PC 3µm and PC 0.22µm filters in the 47-mm filter holders
2. Take out the number of SPE cartridges to be used during this sampling and condition them as follows
3. Dispense 5 mL of MeOH (HPLC grade) into the cartridge. Attach the cartridge to the manifold (remove the stopper first) and let MeOH flow through by gravity or vacuum.
4. Pour 5 mL distilled water into cartridge and let it flow through by gravity or vacuum. The cartridge should be wet at the beginning of the extraction.
5. Once distilled water has passed through, add another 5 mL water before starting sample filtration. This ensures that no air bubbles form in the sorbent bed during extraction.
6. Rinse the Luer adapter with **MQW** and insert it on top of the SPE cartridge and connect the outflow tube of the filtration system

Starting the filtration:

1. Wipe the intake (sample side) tube with **EtOH** in your glove and then rinse with **MQW**, and insert it in the first 2-L sample bottle.
2. Make sure that the vacuum pump downstream of the manifold is ON
3. Open the “bleeding valves” on the two 47-mm filtration units
4. Start the peristaltic pump
5. Close the “bleeding valves” when the heads are purged from air and water flows out
6. There should be a steady “stream” of seawater in the SPE cartridge, otherwise you need to open the “bleeding valves” and purge the 47-mm filtration units

<!> START the chronometer

Once the first 2-L bottle has completely gone through the SPE cartridge:

<!> Leave the peristaltic pump running and open the “bleeding valves” on the two filtration units

<!> Do not stop the chronometer, but write the filtration time on the logsheet (in comments)

1. Disconnect the outflow tube of the filtration system from the SPE cartridge, and remove the Luer adaptor; Rinse the adaptor with **MQW**, and put it back in its clean container
2. Let the outflow tube of the filtration system hang in front of the working bench
3. Wash the cartridge with one full column-load of MilliQ water and keep the pump running empty until the cartridge is dry (ca. 2 min).
4. Remove the cartridge

<!> put the stopper back on the manifold, otherwise it may affect the other filtrations

5. Put the cartridge in its Falcon tube and store it temporarily in the ice box in the fume hood
6. Transfer the sample as soon as possible to the -20°C freezer in the front storage area (F-Store)

Continuing the filtration

1. Wipe the intake (sample side) tube with **EtOH** in your glove and then rinse with **MQW**, and insert it in the second 2-L sample bottle.
2. Remove the plug from the manifold and connect the outflow tube of the filtration system
3. Close the “bleeding valves” when the heads are purged from air and water flows out
4. When the second 2-L sample bottle is empty, open the “bleeding valves” and repeat steps 1-3 with the third 2-L sample bottle
5. When the third 2-L sample bottle is empty, **<!> or after 90 minutes**, remove the intake tube from the sample bottle and let all seawater left in the tubing pass through the filtration system

<!> STOP the chronometer and note the filtration time on the logsheet

<!> If there is still seawater in the sample bottle, measure it and write on the logsheet the volume that passed through the filters, i.e. 6 L or 4 L minus the volume left in the last sample bottle

6. Leave the peristaltic pump running and open the “bleeding valves” on the two filtration units
7. Open the filtration units and use clean tweezers to fold the filters and transfer them into 4-mL glass vials.
8. Store the vials temporarily in the ice box in the fume hood
9. Transfer the samples as soon as possible to the -20°C freezer in the front storage area (F-Store)

<!> Rinse the 2-L sample bottles with fresh water, fill one with 1 L of MilliQ water and rinse the filtration system

Metabolomics – MB20 – targeting unicellular eukaryotes

Contact: Georg Pohnert (georg.pohnert@uni-jena.de) University of Jena, Germany

CAUTION – This protocol is very sensitive to contamination from the skin

- Wear Nitrile gloves at all time
- Always clean tweezers with EtOH and then MilliQ water before use

Step-by-Step

1. Thoroughly rinse one 47-mm filter holder and cup with **MQW**
2. Place a 10-µm PC filter on the filter holder and place the cup on top
3. Gently but thoroughly mix the 250-mL glass bottles and pour ca. 100 mL in the filtration cup
4. Switch on the suction; Gradually add more volume, always mixing the glass bottle before pouring; Not too much at a time in case the filter clogs
5. **<!/ Do not exceed 15 minutes** for the filtrations; keep the remaining volume in the glass bottles to measure the unfiltered volume in a graduated cylinder
6. Switch off the suction as soon as the filter gets dry
7. Thoroughly rinse the cup with **FSW**, using a little suction to drain; Repeat as needed and remove the cup
8. Using two dissecting tweezers, fold the filter in half without touching the sample with the tweezers and without "crushing" the filter too much.
9. Insert the filter into a 4-ml glass vial and store the vial at -20 °C
10. **<!/ write on the logsheet the total volume filtered**
11. Thoroughly rinse the 47mm filter holder, cup and cylinders with **FRW**; re-assemble the filter holders and cups; rinse with **EtOH**

Phenomics – HP – pigments (HPLC)

Contact: Joséphine Ras, Céline Dimier (SAPIGH; celine.dimier@imev-mer.fr)

CAUTION - Cells & pigments may be modified, degraded or lost by:

- **Time spent in the 2L-bottle** - Filter as soon as water is drawn from the rosette. If some bottles have to wait, keep them cool and in the dark space.
- **Light** - Either close the lights in the S-Lab or cover the bottles with black plastic cover.
- **Time spent on a dry filter** – Immediately package & store filters once the filtration is finished.
- **Too much suction** – The vacuum should not exceed 0.04 cm Hg (0.0005 bar) (0.008 PSI).

Step-by-Step

- **Clean the filtering device:** Use the rinse-bottle with **MQW** to clean the inside of the filter holders and funnels while the suction is on. Cover each funnel with aluminum foil.
- **Position the filters:** Use clean tweezers (tips standing in **EtOH** and rinsed with **MQW** before use) to handle the filters. The GF/F filters must be well centered to avoid leaks. Position them on the filtration head, always with the unsquared side up. Switch on the pump and open the valves; the suction will "stick" the filters in the right position; install the funnels on top; switch off the pump.
- **Fill the 2L-bottles up to the top** and close them with the caps: The 2L-bottles are pre-labeled with a sampling depth label (Z0-Z10). From cast to cast, the Niskin Bottles (numbered 1 to 12) collect water from different depths. You must refer to the sampling plan (see oceano engineer) to determine which Niskin bottle corresponds to which depth label.
- **Start filtrations:** Put on the caps with the siphon system; Position and secure the 2L-Bottles on the filtration system; Switch on the pump; Start the chronometer or note the start-time on the logsheet.
- **End filtrations:** Close a valve as soon as its filter dries out; Stop the chronometer and note the duration on the logsheet or note the end-time on the logsheet; Remove the 2L-Bottle and the funnel; Make sure to have in hand the 2mL-cryotube that has the corresponding label; Fold the filter in four, always using clean tweezers, and place it in the cryotube.
- **<!/> Do not rinse the filtration cups** before removing the filters
- **Store the filters:** temporarily in the -20° freezer in the S-Lab and later transfer them in the liquid nitrogen (Dewar #2) labeled "HPLC" in the W-Lab. Do not leave the filtrations unattended to do this. Do not leave tubes with filters on the filtration bench.
- **Time limit:** The standard protocol is to filter the entire 2L-Bottle (2.27 L), but this volume can be reduced if the water is highly charged with particles. As a rule, end the filtration after maximum 45 minutes. If so, close the siphon system with its clamp and proceed to end the filtration and store the filter; Measure the volume remaining in the 2L-Bottle with a graduated cylinder; note the volume filtered on the logsheet; Discard the remaining volume.
- **Rinse the filtering device:** Use the rinse-bottle with **MQW** to clean the inside of the filter holders and funnels while the suction is on. Cover each funnel with aluminum foil.

Phenomics – FC – flow-cytometry pico/nano

Contact: Josep “Pep” Gasol, CSIC, Barcelona (pepgasol@icm.csic.es)

x3
TRIPLICATE

CAUTION – Glutaraldehyde and paraformaldehyde are toxic substances

- Wear gloves, handle with care, and read the safety sheet (MSDS)
- The pre-aliquoted cryotubes are kept at -20°C in the freezer (FRZ) in the front storage area (F-Store).

Step-by-Step

1. FC-P: Dispense 1.5 mL of whole seawater into a 2-mL cryotube (**red cap-insert**) pre-aliquoted with 50 µL of a solution of paraformaldehyde 32%
2. FC-G: Dispense 1.5 mL of whole seawater into a 2-mL cryotube (**blue cap-insert**) pre-aliquoted with 30 µL of a solution of Glutaraldehyde 25%
3. FC-GP: Dispense 1.5 mL of whole seawater into a 2-mL cryotube (**green cap-insert**) pre-aliquoted with 17 µL of a solution of Glutaraldehyde 25% and PoloXamer 10%
4. Close the cryotube, and mix gently by inversion
5. Incubate for 15 min in the dark at +4°C in the **RED** thermos container
6. Store in Liquid Nitrogen dewar #3 in the W-Lab

Phenomics – Aerosols AI – Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Contact: Michel Flores, Weizmann Institute (flores@weizmann.ac.il)

Put on gloves and wash your gloves/hands with [EtOH](#)

Step-by-Step

1. The AI filter is in the [BLUE](#) filter holder
2. Open the filter holder and place the “o-ring” sideways in the black stage.
3. Remove the 47-mm-diameter 0.8-μm polycarbonate membrane filter and place it in the petri slide, face up, on the white pad.
4. Place a new filter in the holder and close.
5. Store the petri slide in the “aerosols sample box” at room temperature (RT) in the F-Store

Phenomics – FM5 – e-HCFM nano

Contact: Rainer Pepperkok, EMBL (rainer.pepperkok@embl.org)

CAUTION – This protocol uses toxic substances

Read PFA & Gluta MSDS

Wear gloves and work in the fume hood

Pre-aliquoted 50-mL Falcon tubes are stored at -20°C in the freezer (FRZ)

Step-by-Step

1. Thoroughly rinse a 50-mL graduated cylinder with **MQW**
2. Measure 45 mL of the gently mixed sample material from the 250-mL bottle into the cylinder
3. Pour the 45-mL into a 50-mL Falcon tube pre-aliquoted with 5 mL of 10% PFA + 500 µl of 25% glutaraldehyde
4. Gently invert the tube a few times and wash the outside of the falcon with fresh water and dry
5. Thoroughly rinse the graduated cylinder with **FRW** and then with **EtOH**
6. Incubate the tube horizontally for min 24h at 4°C in the Fridge.

<24h later>

7. Store the tubes vertically at +4°C in the Fridge

Phenomix – SEM – Scanning Electron Microscopy – pico/nano

C Contact: Ian Probert, CNRS, Station Biologique de Roscoff (probert@sb-roscoff.fr)

Step-by-Step

1. In the W-Lab, setup a 47-mm diameter filtration cup with a 47-mm 0.8- μm polycarbonate membrane
2. Pour 250 ml of whole seawater in the cup, filter, and thoroughly vacuum-dry the membrane under low vacuum
3. Place the filter in a petri-slide and dry it at 60°C for at least 2 hours in the small S-Lab oven*; open the petri-slide cover in the oven
4. Close the petri-slide and store at room temperature in the F-Store

* If the oven is not available, store the petri-slide in the small S-Lab freezer until ready to dry.

Phenomics & Genomics – E5 – single-organism-genomics micro

Contact:

CAUTION:

EtOH may rub-off the information written by hand on the label.

The maximum volume of EtOH in a sample is limited to 15 mL for international shipping

Step-by-Step

1. Pour the content of the 250-mL glass jar onto a 47-mm polycarbonate 3- μ m-pore-size membrane
2. Wash the material off the sides of the filtration cup with **EtOH**
3. Using two dissecting tweezers, roll the filter in half without "crushing" the filter
4. Insert the filter in the 15-mL Falcon tube and let the filter stick to the inside of the tube with the organisms facing the inside of the tube
5. Bring the volume of **EtOH** to 15mL and close the cap tightly
6. Store the 15-mL Falcon tube(s) at -20°C in the Freezer

Phenomics – 3DEM5 – 3D electron microscopy nano

Contact: Yannick Schwab, EMBL (schwab@embl.de)

CAUTION – This protocol uses toxic substances

Read PFA & Gluta MSDS

Wear gloves and work in the fume hood

The toxic liquid wastes (100 mL per sample) are disposed of in the liquid waste container behind the Wetlab

The toxic solid waste (1 filter per sample) is disposed of temporarily in the yellow toxic waste bin in the fumehood and later stored in the solid waste container in the Cale Arrière.

Pre-aliquoted 15-mL Falcon tubes with 11 mL of incubation mix are stored at -20°C in the freezer (FRZ) in the front storage are (F-Store)

Pre-aliquoted 15-mL Falcon tubes with 10 mL of storage cocktail mix are stored at -20°C in the freezer (FRZ) in the front storage are (F-Store)

Step-by-Step

1. 100 ml of sample is poured in a 100-mL black-cap bottle dedicated to aldehyde fixation containing 11 ml of 10X buffered PFA/Glutaraldehyde fixative solution. Check if 111 mL fits in these bottles, otherwise we use the 250-mL red-cap bottles, but the preference is for the bottle to be full... but it also needs to be practical when pouring the incubated seawater in the filtration unit.
2. The sample is stored at 4°C for 24h.

<24h later>

3. Filter the incubated sample on a polycarbonate membrane (47mm diameter, 3 µm pore size) using a dedicated 500ml Nalgene filtration unit in the fumehood. A gentle vacuum (>0.8 bar absolute pressure) is applied until about 2 ml is left above the membrane. To stop the filtration immediately, the vacuum can be broken by opening one of the plugs on the side of the filtration unit. Attention is paid NOT to let the membrane dry.
4. The cells are resuspended by gentle pipetting adding ~10 ml of 1x buffer.
5. The sample is filtered again until ~2 mL is left above the membrane. The cells are detached from the membrane and resuspended by gentle pipetting adding 10 ml of 1x cocktail mix (long term storage fixative).
6. Transfer the cells into 2*5 mL cryotubes in the cocktail mix.
7. Store the tubes horizontally at +4°C in the Fridge

Phenomics – FCAM20 – FlowCam 4x

Contact: Fabien Lombard, LOV (lombard@obs-vlfr.fr)

See Phenomics – Planktoscope-protocol-for-plankton-imaging ([link to protocols.io](#))

Phenomics & Genomics – E20 – single-organism-genomics micro

Contact:

CAUTION:

EtOH may rub-off the information written by hand on the label.

The maximum volume of EtOH in a sample is limited to 15 mL for international shipping

Step-by-Step

1. Thoroughly rinse one 47-mm filter holder and cup with **MQW**
2. Place a 10-µm PC filter on the filter holder and place the cup on top
3. Gently but thoroughly mix the 250-mL glass bottles and pour ca. 100 mL in the filtration cup
4. Switch on the suction; Gradually add more volume, always mixing the glass bottle before pouring; Not too much at a time in case the filter clogs
5. **<!/ Do not exceed 15 minutes** for the filtrations; keep the remaining volume in the glass bottles to measure the unfiltered volume in a graduated cylinder
6. Switch off the suction as soon as the filter gets dry
7. Thoroughly rinse the cup with **FSW**, using a little suction to drain; Repeat as needed and remove the cup
8. Wash the material off the sides of the filtration cup with **EtOH**
9. Using two dissecting tweezers, fold the filter in half without touching the sample with the tweezers and without "crushing" the filter too much.
10. Insert the filter in the 15-mL Falcon tube and let the filter stick to the inside of the tube with the organisms facing the inside of the tube
11. Bring the volume of **EtOH** to 15mL and close the cap tightly
12. Store the 15-mL Falcon tube(s) at -20°C in the Freezer
13. **<!/ write on the logsheet the total volume filtered**
14. Thoroughly rinse the 47mm filter holder, cup and cylinders with **FRW**; re-assemble the filter holders and cups; rinse with **EtOH**

<24h later>

15. Change the **EtOH** if it is coloured

Phenomics – FM20 – e-HCFM micro

Contact: Rainer Pepperkok, EMBL (rainer.pepperkok@embl.org)

CAUTION – This protocol uses toxic substances

Read PFA & Gluta MSDS

Wear gloves and work in the fume hood

Pre-aliquot sample containers – store in the fridge

Step-by-Step

16. Thoroughly rinse a 50-mL graduated cylinder with **MQW**
17. Gently but thoroughly mix the 250-mL sample and pour 45 mL in a 50-mL graduated cylinder
18. Pour the 45-mL into a 50-mL Falcon tube pre-aliquoted with 5 mL of 10% PFA + 500 µl of 25% glutaraldehyde
19. Gently invert the tube a few times and wash the outside of the falcon with fresh water and dry
20. Thoroughly rinse the graduated cylinder with **FRW** and then with **EtOH**
21. Incubate the tube horizontally for a min 24h at 4°C in the Fridge.

<24h later>

22. Store the tubes vertically at +4°C in the Fridge

Phenomics – 3DEM20 – 3D electron microscopy micro

Contact: Rainer Pepperkok, EMBL (rainer.pepperkok@embl.org)

CAUTION – This protocol uses toxic substances

Read PFA & Gluta MSDS

Wear gloves and work in the fume hood

Pre-aliquot sample containers – store in the fridge

Step-by-Step

1. 2*45 ml (duplicates) of sample is poured in falcon tubes containing 5 ml of 10X buffered PFA/Glutaraldehyde fixative solution.
2. The samples are stored upright at 4°C for 24h.
3. After 24h, the samples should form a pellet.
4. Supernatant is removed (40ml) and replaced by 1x storage fixative.
5. Tubes are then stored at 4°C horizontally. Never freeze

Phenomics – LU20 – taxonomy

Contact:

Step-by-Step

1. Gently but thoroughly mix the 100-mL container and pour the remaining 45 mL of concentrate into a 50 mL Falcon tube
2. Add 1 mL of Lugol's solution
3. Store at in the dark (sample box) at +4°C (alternatively at room temperature)

Phenomics – F200 – ZooScan

Contact: Fabien Lombard, LOV (lombard@obs-vlfr.fr)

CAUTION: Toxic substance

Step-by-Step

- Thoroughly rinse the 200- μ m sieve with fresh water
- Progressively pour the content of the cod-end into the 200- μ m sieve
- Rinse the cod-end with **FSW** until no more plankton is visible in the cod-end
- Concentrate sample on one side of the sieve using the **FSW** squeeze bottle
- Pour the sample in a 250-mL red-cap bottle, and rinse the sieve upside down directly into the bottle using **FSW**
- *<The quantity of material should never exceed 1/3 of the bottle capacity>* If it is the case, divide the sample in several 250-mL bottles and make a clear note on the Logsheet.
- Add 30mL of non-buffered formol using the dispenser in the Fume Hood in the W-Lab
- Complete with **BORAX** to a final volume of 250 mL, leaving an air space below the neck of the bottle (see flowchart)
- Close the bottle with its inside cap liner and the red cap, and rinse it with fresh water
- Store the sample at room temperature (RT) in the front storage area (F-Store)

Phenomics & Genomics – E200 – sorting single-organism

Contact:

CAUTION:

EtOH may rub-off the information written by hand on the label.

The maximum volume of EtOH in a sample is limited to 15 mL for international shipping

Step-by-Step

1. Thoroughly rinse one 47-mm filter holder and cup with **MQW**
 2. Place a 10-µm PC filter on the filter holder and place the cup on top
 3. Gently but thoroughly mix the 250-mL glass bottles and pour ca. 100 mL in the filtration cup
 4. Switch on the suction; Gradually add more volume, always mixing the glass bottle before pouring; Not too much at a time in case the filter clogs
 5. **<!/ Do not exceed 15 minutes** for the filtrations; keep the remaining volume in the glass bottles to measure the unfiltered volume in a graduated cylinder
 6. Switch off the suction as soon as the filter gets dry
 7. Thoroughly rinse the cup with **FSW**, using a little suction to drain; Repeat as needed and remove the cup
 8. Wash the material off the sides of the filtration cup with **EtOH**
 9. Using two dissecting tweezers, fold the filter in half without touching the sample with the tweezers and without "crushing" the filter too much.
 10. Insert the filter in the 15-mL Falcon tube and let the filter stick to the inside of the tube with the organisms facing the inside of the tube
 11. Bring the volume of **EtOH** to 15mL and close the cap tightly
 12. Store the 15-mL Falcon tube(s) at -20°C in the Freezer
 13. **<!/ write on the logsheet the total volume filtered**
 14. Thoroughly rinse the 47mm filter holder, cup and cylinders with **FRW**; re-assemble the filter holders and cups; rinse with **EtOH**
- <24h later>**
15. Change the **EtOH** if it is coloured

Phenomix – MP300 – Microscopic imaging of the plastisphere

Contact: Jean-François Ghiglione, CNRS, LOMIC (ghiglione@obs-banyuls.fr)

CAUTION: Paraformaldehyde is toxic

Step-by-Step

1. Package the smaller part in a 2-mL cryotube
2. Label the cryotube and the logsheet with a barcode sticker
3. Using the clean forceps, gently transfer the smaller part in a 2-mL cryotube pre-aliquoted with ca. 500 μ L of 4% paraformaldehyde. Invert 3-5 times to make sure the plastic is immersed in the solution.
4. Clean the forceps after handling each piece of plastic so you don't cross-contaminate.
5. Temporarily store the sample in a cool dark box for 2-3 hours*.

<!> IMPORTANT: After 2-3 hours the piece needs to be transferred from paraformaldehyde to 50:50 (v:v) PBS:EtOH buffer. The easiest way is to use a disposable transfer pipet to remove the paraformaldehyde. Do this in the W-Lab fume-hood and dispose of the waste in the liquid waste container behind the W-Lab.

6. After removing the paraformaldehyde, add 1 ml of ethanol:PBS to each tube using a clean pipet by drawing up to the 4th mark
7. store in refrigerator or minus 20 freezer (they will not freeze because of the ethanol).

Phenomics – F680 & F2000 – ZooScan

Contact: Fabien Lombard, LOV (lombard@obs-vlfr.fr)

CAUTION: Toxic substance

Step-by-Step F680

1. Thoroughly rinse the 200- μ m sieve and a small funnel with **MQW**
2. Pour the content of the cod-end into the 200- μ m sieve
3. Rinse the cod-end with **FSW** until no more plankton is visible in the cod-end
4. Concentrate sample on one side of the sieve using the **FSW** squeeze bottle
5. Pour the sample in a 250-mL red-cap bottle, and rinse the sieve upside down directly into the funnel using the **BORAX** squeeze bottle
6. *<The quantity of material should never exceed 1/4 of the bottle capacity>* If it is the case, divide the sample in several 250-mL bottles and make a clear note on the Logsheet.
7. Rinse the 200- μ m sieve and funnel with Borax until no plankton sticks on the side
8. Add 30mL of non-buffered formol using the dispenser in the Fume Hood in the W-Lab
9. Complete with Borax to a final volume of 250 mL, leaving an air space below the neck of the bottle; Close the bottle and rinse it with fresh water
10. Label the bottle with station #, depth, and size fraction, e.g. “MM-001”, “0-150m” and “>200”
11. Store the sample at room temperature in the F-Store

Step-by-Step F2000

Preserve and store the sample as in protocol **F680** above

Phenomix & Genomics – E2000 – sorting single organisms

Contact:

CAUTION:

EtOH may rub-off the information written by hand on the label.

The maximum volume of EtOH in a sample is limited to 15 mL for international shipping

Step-by-Step E2000

1. Label the 250-mL red-cap bottle *<!/> on the side AND on the cap* with the station number and time of the net deployment
2. Store at -20°C in the Freezer (FRZ) in the front storage area (F-Store)
3. Before shipping, when time allows, individual organisms of interest should be picked and stored individually in 15-mL Falcon tubes with **EtOH**
4. Label the 15-mL Falcon tube with a barcode and stick the replicate barcode on the sample logsheet of the corresponding net

Phenomics & Genomics – E680 & E2000 – sorting single organisms

Contact:

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Step-by-Step

1. Thoroughly rinse one 47-mm filter holder and cup with **MQW**
 2. Place a 10-µm PC filter on the filter holder and place the cup on top
 3. Gently but thoroughly mix the 250-mL glass bottles and pour ca. 100 mL in the filtration cup
 4. Switch on the suction; Gradually add more volume, always mixing the glass bottle before pouring; Not too much at a time in case the filter clogs
 5. **<!/ Do not exceed 15 minutes** for the filtrations; keep the remaining volume in the glass bottles to measure the unfiltered volume in a graduated cylinder
 6. Switch off the suction as soon as the filter gets dry
 7. Thoroughly rinse the cup with **FSW**, using a little suction to drain; Repeat as needed and remove the cup
 8. Wash the material off the sides of the filtration cup with **EtOH**
 9. Using two dissecting tweezers, fold the filter in half without touching the sample with the tweezers and without "crushing" the filter too much.
 10. Insert the filter in the 15-mL Falcon tube and let the filter stick to the inside of the tube with the organisms facing the inside of the tube
 11. Bring the volume of **EtOH** to 15mL and close the cap tightly
 12. Store the 15-mL Falcon tube(s) at -20°C in the Freezer
 13. **<!/ write on the logsheet the total volume filtered**
 14. Thoroughly rinse the 47mm filter holder, cup and cylinders with **FRW**; re-assemble the filter holders and cups; rinse with **EtOH**
- <24h later>**
1. Thoroughly rinse the 200-µm sieve with **MQW**
 2. Gently resuspend the material in the 50-ml Falcon and pour its content into the sieve, using a funnel to discarding the **EtOH** filtrate in the dedicated waste bottle
 3. Rinse the 50-ml Falcon into the sieve using **EtOH**
 4. Wash the material off the 200-µm sieve with **EtOH** into one or two 15-mL Falcon tube(s)
 5. Bring the volume of **EtOH** to 15mL and close the cap tightly

6. Store the 15-mL Falcon tube(s) at -20°C in the Freezer
7. Thoroughly rinse the 20-µm sieve with **FRW** and then with **EtOH**

Step-by-Step E2000

1. Pick one representative individual of each key/dominant “species” and place them in one-to-many 15-mL Falcon tube(s)
2. Bring the volume of **EtOH** to 15mL and close the cap tightly
3. Store the 15-mL Falcon tube(s) at -20°C in the Freezer
4. *<!/ write on the logsheet the number of individuals in each tube*
24h later>
5. Thoroughly rinse the 200-µm sieve with **MQW**
6. Gently resuspend the material in the 50-ml Falcon and pour its content into the sieve, using a funnel to discarding the **EtOH** filtrate in the dedicated waste bottle
7. Rinse the 15-ml Falcon into the sieve using **EtOH**
8. Wash the material off the 200-µm sieve with **EtOH** back into the 15-mL Falcon tube(s)
9. Bring the volume of **EtOH** to 15mL and close the cap tightly
10. Store the 15-mL Falcon tube(s) at -20°C in the Freezer
11. Thoroughly rinse the 20-µm sieve with **FRW** and then with **EtOH**

12 Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO – Sampling flowcharts

SAMPLE SPLITTER

Preparing the sample splitter

1. Remove the funnel and the lid from the splitter
2. Put back the funnel in the **OFF-center configuration** (used to split liquids)

Splitting the sample material in 8 aliquots

1. Measure the volume of sample material in the 2-L bottle
 - It should be around **1000 mL**
2. Pour Filtered Sea Water (FSW) in a graduated cylinder
 - The total volume (sample + FSW) must be **1600 mL**
 - Measure the required amount of FSW; it should be around **600 mL**
 - This way each aliquot will be **200 mL**
3. Switch the sample splitter **ON** and wait for it to reach a regular speed
4. Thoroughly, but gently mix the sample and pour it in the sample splitter
 - In 2-3 shots, re-mix each time and pour with a regular flow
5. Rinse the 2-L bottle with half the FSW (keep the other half for the next step)
 - a) Pour half the FSW in the 2-L bottle and thoroughly rinse the inside
 - b) Pour it in the sample splitter
6. Pour the remaining FSW directly in the sample splitter to rinse the splitting funnel
7. Switch the sample splitter **OFF**
8. Refer to the labels on the 8 bottles to process the aliquots

When all the aliquots are processed

1. Empty the 250-mL glass jars and put them back in place on the sample splitter (**align the arrows and turn clockwise**)
2. Switch the sample splitter **ON** and wait for it to reach a regular speed
3. Pour 1 L of MilliQ water (or fresh water) in the sample splitter
4. Switch the sample splitter **OFF**
5. Rinse and empty each bottle, and put them back on the splitter

At the end of the day

1. Leave the clean glass bottles upside down on a paper towel in a tray
2. Put back the lid of the splitter and place the funnel in its centred position

